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REPORT ON THE RESULTS OF EVALUATION SYSTEM OF SOCIO-EDUCATIONAL INTEGRATION OF MIGRANTCHILDREN

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Summary

This report operationalises the aim of creating a dashboard of indicators about the integration of refugee and migrant children in schools and other experiential environments in Europe is evaluated (measure and monitor). An assessment of the methodology and results of the IMMERSE research methodology implemented in WP1 is presented in detail.

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1 INTRODUCTION

IMMERSE WP1 focuses on implementing a research methodology with the objective of creating a dashboard of indicators that will evaluate (measure and monitor) the integration of refugee and migrant children in schools and other experiential environments in Europe. In this deliverable we describe and assess this methodology and its results.

The research methodology implemented involves an academic pillar (which provides the scientific bases of the dashboard) and a co-creation pillar (which ensures the relevance of the dashboard from the point of view of the relevant stakeholders and of policy-making). Additionally, the use of co-creation methods promotes the empowerment and participation of migrant and refugee children (one of the most vulnerable groups in Europe) as well as the participation on an equal footing of very different stakeholders (e.g. governmental and non-governmental) and the application of a whole-school approach (all members of the educational community, including the students, have been included). The double-pillar nature of the methodology has been implemented in its two main phases, which are discussed in the remainder of this paper: (1) Definition of the parameters of the dashboard and selection of contents and (2) Selection and refinement of empirical indicators.

2 DEFINITION OF PARAMETERS AND SELECTION OF CONTENTS OF THE DASHBOARD

The scientific bases of the dashboard were built starting with a literature review of the fields of migrant integration and socio-educational inclusion of children, which helped define a first outline of the dashboard parameters and a mapping exercise of all possible relevant contents, identifying the relations among them (see Conceptual Framework (2019)¹). In parallel, a series of workshops and consultations were conducted to gather the perspective of different stakeholders, including children, at the micro, meso and macro levels in all 6 IMMERSE countries (Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy and Spain). These workshops provided a thick perspective of the integration processes of migrant children of different backgrounds and experiences across Europe, and their main barriers and facilitators, according to the multiple perspectives of all relevant stakeholders. The results were analysed to find those most robust across stakeholders and countries. The findings were contrasted with those of the literature review, obtaining a high degree of alignment, and they were used to refine the parameters of the dashboard and to select and shape the contents to be included. The use of co-creation methods from the beginning of the research process helps ensure the involvement and ownership of children and all other relevant stakeholders as a core part of the methodology, which will help ensure the adequacy and relevance of the dashboard as an evaluation system for migrant children's socio-educational integration.

¹ Serrano Sanguilinda, I., Fernández García, M., Ordóñez Carabaño, Á., Bajo Marcos, E., & Miguel Somavilla, S. (2019). *Common Conceptual Framework*.

2.1 ACADEMIC PILLAR: THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

A conceptual framework was developed that provides the scientific bases for the dashboard. This conceptual framework built on a literature review that interlinked, from a multidisciplinary perspective, two largely independent bodies of literature: the literature on migrant integration (and the more subject-specific research on migrant children) and the literature on socio-educative inclusion and child development (and the more subject-specific research on migrant children).

To that end, a search was launched on 27 bibliographic databases, including only indexed and peer-reviewed sources.² The search included six key words (migrant*; child*; inclusion; integration; education*; intercultural*) using the three main fields (Title, Abstract and/or Keywords). This first search resulted in 526 articles, which were all consulted. We excluded sources that were too specialised in highly specific areas of each field, that did not provide theoretical foundations and that were not sufficiently empirically supported. Additionally, experts on these fields, as well partners, were asked to identify and suggest key authors and key sources, which were also incorporated. This process granted a comprehensive review with the aim of establishing an overarching conceptual framework for integration that was (1) child-centered (2) anchored in the multiple and heterogeneous experiences of migration and (3) grounded in ecological systems of human development allowing to stablish relationships on the different levels of psycho-social interaction.

The review included conceptual and methodological debates, existing analytical frameworks, empirical evidence and normative debates around integration. We first reviewed existing attempts to conceptualize integration processes and their multiple inter-related dimensions (Esser 2001; Heckmann & Schnapper 2003; Ager & Strang, 2004; Lacroix 2013; Garcés-Mascreñas & Penninx, 2016). The review also included existing attempts to measure these processes through indicators: several such attempts exist (largely identifying structural and cultural dimensions of integration) but none that is specific to refugee and migrant children. By incorporating the contributions made in the field of socio-educational inclusion, IMMERSE enlarged this vision into a more grounded perspective of the specific challenges and barriers faced by refugee and migrant children during their adaptation and settling to the host societies. This literature emphasizes the centrality of schools for children's short-term and long-term results, as well as their complex interactions with different individual and situational factors at several levels (micro, meso, macro), the mechanisms behind these interactions, and the assessment of different approaches. Next, a co-creation process among the partners was carried out reviewing specialized literature on three thematic areas of refugee and migrant children integration: psycho-social well-being, intercultural competences and multilingualism and gender. The documents generated paid attention to the core results and outcomes to be considered from the point of view of integration of children specifically, and their main determinants. The joint results of this literature review provided the scientific bases for conceptualizing and providing an analytical framework for children's integration processes.

This literature review provided the scientific bases for conceptualizing children's integration processes and an analytical framework that would provide the foundations for the dashboard of indicators. Social indicators are "*statistics, statistical series or any form of indication that makes it*

² We did not limit the publication date and included different types of sources (journal articles, books, conference proceedings, thesis, technical reports and reviews).

easier for us to study where we are and where we are going with respect to certain objectives and goals, as well as to evaluate specific programs and determine its impact" (Horn, 1993, p. 147). In short, an indicator is an instrument that serves to observe what is essential about the considered objectives and goals, as well as about the process leading to them, which is complex and we cannot directly observe. To define this information system it is necessary to (1) identify the **goals and objectives**, (2) the **processes and outcomes** that bring us closer to those goals, and (3) the criteria to select and process the **specific data** (García Cívico, 2010). The literature review provided the bases to define these three components, as detailed below.

Goals and objectives

The definition of the goals and objectives of integration requires a normative framework that helps select and prioritize among different results. For IMMERSE, the normative framework is given by the inclusive and intercultural models set out by UNESCO (1994, 2006)³ and the Council of Europe (2008)⁴. The main objectives of integration under this framework are:

- (1) that migrant (and other) children reach their **full potential**
- (2) that migrant (and other) children, as well as their families, become an **accepted part of society as fully recognized members at the formal and informal levels**.

Processes and outcomes (that bring us closer to those goals)

Building on the literature review, IMMERSE has identified 5 key **outcome dimensions** that define children's integration outcomes – i.e. in terms of reaching their full potential and become fully recognized members of society at the formal and informal levels. These dimensions are: legal status and rights, language and culture, well-being, social relations and educational achievements. These outcome dimensions are complex, multidimensional and interrelated. The identified outcomes are furthermore mediated by personal as well as situational factors, constituting **facilitators and barriers** that sustain, foster or handicap the achievement or improvement of the

³ Inclusive models consider diversity positive and a stimulus for fostering learning in the context of education. These models promote equality, emphasizing the responsibility to ensure the groups with a higher risk of exclusion are active parts of their community and educational system. Inclusion –when referred to socio-educative inclusion – consists of the presence, participation and achievement of all students and it is process-based, as the aim is to continuously look for better ways to respond to diversity (Ainscow, 2016). In this respect, the UNESCO's Salamanca statement of 1994 explicitly remarks, "*The fundamental principle of the inclusive school is that all children should learn together, wherever possible, regardless of any difficulties or differences they may have. Inclusive schools must recognize and respond to the diverse needs of their students, accommodating both different styles and rates of learning and ensuring quality education to all through appropriate curricula, organizational arrangements, teaching strategies, resource use and partnerships with their communities*". And the UNESCO Guidelines on Intercultural Education (2006) states three principles for guaranteeing the educational rights of children: (1) Intercultural Education respects the cultural identity of the learner through the provision of culturally appropriate and responsive quality education for all (2) provides every learner with the cultural knowledge, attitudes and skills necessary to achieve active and full participation in society and (3) provides all learners with cultural knowledge, attitudes and skills that enable them to contribute to respect, understanding and solidarity among individuals, ethnic, social, cultural and religious groups and nations.

⁴ Interculturalism defines integration as a two-way process in which both minorities and majorities make accommodations towards each other. Interculturalism values cultural diversity and pluralism and assumes that cultures are not fixed, but plural and permeable. Additionally, it emphasizes intercultural dialogue as a way to foster understanding and to reduce prejudice and stereotypes in public life. Intercultural education brings the principles of interculturalism to schools in order to realize the full potential of all students, including migrant and native children (UNESCO, 2018).

considered outcomes. Following an ecological approach (Bronfenbrenner, 1994), these determinants can be found at the micro, meso and macro levels, which we define following a child-perspective (i.e. in terms of levels of proximity to the child):

(1) **Micro**: the child and his/her family

(2) **Meso**: school, neighbourhood and other primary places in their daily life, including all possible relations at this “local” level, from small groups to formal organizations (e.g. associations, social services, etc.) (McLeod & Lively, 2003).

(3) **Macro**: the policies and large political, economic and social systems of a given society. This includes the vertical dimension of policymaking, that is, the relationship between the national, regional, and local levels (Penninx & Garces Mascarenas, 2016).

The mapping of all these determinants and levels of observation, as identified in the literature, results in a complex web of mutual dependencies across dimensions and spheres of intervention, which we reflected in a two-way matrix – with outcomes in the columns, and outcomes and determinants in the rows – mapping out direct relationships between outcomes, on the one hand, and between outcomes and determinants, on the other hand. This matrix cannot be reported in this document due to its large size, but it was used as a reference for the ensuing selection process.

Finally, integration is conceived as a **process** (Penninx & Garces Mascarenas, 2016) and as such, the conceptualization of outcome and process indicators should be as dynamic as possible. For instance, in the dimension of legal status, the emphasis is put on the possibility to acquire superior statuses up to the point of ensuring full security, stability and formal membership in society (i.e. citizenship). It is also important to incorporate into the observation all the responsible **actors** involved in this process: under the inclusive and intercultural framework, the responsibility for integration goals rests with migrants themselves,⁵ the host government and institutions,⁶ and native communities.⁷

Criteria to select and process the specific data

It is important to underline the complexity and multi-dimensionality of the outcomes to be measured, as well as that of the web of interactions that determine such outcomes. The main function of the dashboard of indicators is to capture the essence of these processes with a limited amount of information, i.e., simplifying the way we observe reality by selecting key aspects that allow us to reach conclusions on a much broader and complex reality. With this aim, the main criteria for the selection of the final contents of the dashboard were the following:

(1) The most important criterion was **robustness**. The key outcomes and determinants to be included would be those gathering the most consensus about their importance and

⁵ According to the European Commission, their main responsibility is “to respect the fundamental norms and values of the host society and participate actively in the integration process, without having to relinquish their own identity (European Commission, 2005)

⁶ According to the European Commission: “it is the responsibility of the host society to ensure that the formal rights of immigrants are in place in such a way that the individual has the possibility of participating in economic, social, cultural and civil life” (European Commission, 2005).

⁷ According to the Council of the EU, integration is a dynamic process of mutual accommodation by all residents of Member States that implies respect for the basic values of the European Union (Council of the European Union, 2004)

relevance both within the literature and across the different stakeholders (academic and co-creation pillars of the pre-selection phase). Similarly, the empirical indicators selected to measure these outcomes and determinants must concite consensus about their validity and empirical robustness, both among experts and among the consulted stakeholders (content and ecological validation phases). However, the robustness criterion alone was unlikely to suffice, since the outcomes and determinants that are important and relevant are, by the nature of the object of study, numerous and complex.

- (2) Another necessary criterion was **efficiency**, which is capturing the most with the least information possible, i.e. maximizing the explanatory power of the selected information. For instance, in terms of outcomes, some of the identified subdimensions may be strongly interconnected or more telling than others. In the case of determinants, some of them have a significant impact on multiple outcomes, making them particularly informative and relevant given their higher explanatory power. Similarly, and in order to ensure the sustainability as well as the general efficiency of the dashboard, the empirical indicators selected to measure these outcomes and determinants should be preferably **already available and produced in a regular and sustainable manner** (in order to observe the evolution of the indicators and relevant trends).⁸ The number of indicators that require ad-hoc or specific collection should be kept to a minimum in order to improve the sustainability prospects of the dashboard. Policy recommendations will be developed in order to include them in existing or future initiatives of regular data collection.⁹
- (3) Close to the criterion of efficiency is the criterion of **policy relevance**: since one of the main objectives of a dashboard of indicators is to evaluate programs and provide policy recommendations that can bring us closer to the established goals, policy relevance (i.e. the possibility and potential impact of intervention) is a major criterion to have into account.

2.2 CO-CREATION PILLAR: STAKEHOLDERS PERSPECTIVE

In order to gather and incorporate the perspective of all relevant stakeholders, including children, into the definition of the dashboard, a series of workshops and consultations were conducted at the identified levels (micro, meso and macro) in all 6 IMMERSE countries (Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy and Spain), in parallel to the literature review discussed above. These workshops paid particular attention to:

- (1) The empowerment and participation of migrant and refugee children, as well as to reflecting the multiple backgrounds and experiences of different children. First, a Children's Research Advisory Group CRAG¹⁰ was created at the beginning of the project and consulted about the

⁸ Two important requirements must be met by these data. First, that they are produced by reliable and trusted sources, as transparent as possible in the elaboration of the data. Second, that the data are produced and available across different contexts, allowing the comparison between countries and regions.

⁹ Meanwhile, IMMERSE will collect these indicators in two cross-country surveys of children and schools in 2020 and then again 2021.

¹⁰ The IMMERSE Children's Research Advisory Group (CRAG) is composed by 10-15 migrant and refugee children who are resident in Ireland and who continuously provide advice on the development of data collection instruments, data analysis and dissemination to the project.

different steps and methodologies proposed. Second, in each of the countries, several workshops were conducted with children in selected age ranges (6-9, 10-13, 14-16, 17-18) as part of the co-creation pillar.¹¹

- (2) Extensive and specific representation of all other relevant stakeholders on an equal footing: families (parents), meso-level actors (schools and educators, associations, NGOs, municipalities, etc.) and policy-makers and experts at the regional and national levels.
- (3) A whole school approach: all members of the educational community participated, including teachers and professors, managerial teams, parents' associations, administration staff, etc.

These workshops provided a thick perspective of the integration processes of migrant children of different backgrounds and experiences across Europe, and the main barriers and facilitators for these integration processes, according to the multiple perspectives of all relevant stakeholders. The goal was to refine, reshape and if necessary expand the conclusions of the literature review concerning the identification of key outcomes and determinants of refugee and migrant children's integration.

Table 1. Proposed qualitative workshops/research activities (minimum)

TOPIC	PARTNERS	MICRO	MESO	MACRO
Intercultural competences	Comillas	4 workshops with children (ages: 6-9, 10-12, 13-16, 17-18) 1 workshop with parents	1 focus group / world café	6-10 expert interviews
	SCIT	4 workshops with children (ages: 6-9, 10-12, 13-16, 17-18) 1 workshop with parents	1 focus group / world café	6-10 expert interviews
Psychosocial wellbeing	UCC	4 workshops with children (ages: 6-9, 10-12, 13-16, 17-18) 1 workshop with parents	1 focus group / world café	6-10 expert interviews
	PANTEION	4 workshops with children (ages: 6-9, 10-12, 13-16, 17-18) 1 workshop with parents	1 focus group / world café	6-10 expert interviews
Gender issues	DOZ	4 workshops with children (ages: 6-9, 10-12, 13-16, 17-18) 1 workshop with parents	1 focus group / world café	6-10 expert interviews
	ACE	4 workshops with children (ages: 6-9, 10-12, 13-16, 17-18) 1 workshop with parents	1 focus group / world café	6-10 expert interviews

Methodology

These research activities were organized thematically by pairs of countries: (1) linguistic and cultural issues in Spain and Italy; (2) wellbeing issues in Ireland and Greece; and (3) gender issues in Germany and Belgium. These themes were subjected to discussion in each pair of countries during specific research activities organized for micro-level actors (children's and parents' workshops), meso-level actors (world cafés with broad participation from schools, informal

¹¹ In these workshops we ensured the diversification of participants by sex, origin, place of birth (first and second generations), circumstances of arrival and specific categories (e.g. asylum seekers, refugees, unaccompanied minors).

educational centres, associations, NGOs and public administration at the local level) and macro-level actors (interviews with authorities at regional and national level and experts). A total of 33 workshops with children and parents, 9 world cafés with educational and local communities, and 39 interviews with policy makers were conducted, totalling 420 child and adult participants.

Table 2. Final composition of the activities and samples of participants

COUNTRY	ACTIVITIES	NUMBER OF ACTIVITIES	ECOLOGICAL LEVEL	N	TOTAL
Ireland	Workshops with children	1 workshop Children 6-9 yrs.	MICRO	6	68
		1 workshop Children 10-12yrs		7	
		1 workshop Children 13- 16 yrs.		6	
		2 workshops youth 16-18 yrs.		15	
	Workshop with parents	1 workshop with parents		25	
	World café/Focus group	2 focus groups	MESO	15	
	Interviews	8 interviews	MACRO	8	
Greece	Workshops with children	2 workshop Children 6-9 yrs.	MICRO	11	115
		2 workshop Children 10-12yrs		14	
		3 workshop Children 13- 16 yrs.		26	
		2 workshops youth 16-18 yrs.		16	
	Workshop with parents	1 workshop with parents		9	
	World café/Focus group	2 world cafes and 3 interviews	MESO	36	
	Interviews	3 interviews	MACRO	3	
Spain	Workshops with children	1 workshop Children 6-9 yrs.	MICRO	5	64
		1 workshop Children 10-12yrs		8	
		1 workshop Children 13- 16 yrs.		7	
		1 workshops youth 16-18 yrs.		5	
	Workshop with parents	1 workshop with parents		8	
	World café/Focus group	1 World café	MESO	25	
	Interviews	6 interviews	MACRO	6	
Italy	Workshops with children	1 workshop Children 6-9 yrs.	MICRO	6	79
		1 workshop Children 10-12yrs		9	
		1 workshop Children 13- 16 yrs.		7	
		1 workshops youth 16-18 yrs.		12	
	Workshop with parents	1 workshop with parents		10	
	World café/Focus group	1World Café + 1 Focus Group	MESO	26	
	Interviews	9 interviews	MACRO	9	
Germany	Workshops with children	1 workshop Children 6-9 yrs.	MICRO	9	55
		1 workshop Children 10-12yrs		12	
		1 workshop Children 13- 16 yrs.		6	
		1 workshops youth 16-18 yrs.		6	
	Workshop with parents	1 workshop with parents		14	
	World café/Focus group	1 Focus Group	MESO	8	
	Interviews	6 interviews	MACRO	6	
Belgium	Workshops with children	1 workshop Children 6-9 yrs.	MICRO	15	49
		1 workshop Children 10-12yrs		7	

		1 workshop Children 13- 16 yrs.		7	
		1 workshops youth 16-18 yrs.		5	
	Workshop with parents	1 workshop with parents		4	
	World café/ Focus group	2 Focus groups	MESO	5	
	Interviews	6 interviews	MACRO	6	
				TOTAL	430

The common parameters for all these research activities emphasized the use of broad and open questions, aiming at depicting the integration process of the children, and identifying their main barriers and facilitators. The goal was to unearth the stakeholders' perspectives on the key outcomes and determinants of children's integration, without pre-imposing any of the categories or findings from the literature review. All workshops and sessions were recorded and produced transcripts or/and exhaustive notes, as well as additional materials, such as the summaries of the world café discussions by the moderators, and graphic outputs by the children. The qualitative analysis explored these outputs in an inductive manner, identifying the relevant themes that emerged about the three organizing topics and their intersection with integration. The analysis also focused on identifying those findings most robust across stakeholders and countries.

Results

Research on the three thematic areas of psycho-social well-being, language and culture and gender provided individual outcomes of integration such as specific skills (e.g. language acquisition, intercultural skills, conflict resolution and problem solving), conducts (e.g. social roles, performance in the school), cognitions (e.g. individual and social identity, expectations, attributions, beliefs...), emotions (e.g. happiness, hope) and needs (e.g. achievement, belonging), that result from the accommodation and adaptation processes that take place during the integration process of migrant-background children and adolescents. In addition, group and social outcomes such as social connections/networks or social capital that serve as pathways for the transmission of values, attitudes, and behaviours emerged too as crucial in the integration process. The following table summarizes all the outcomes of migrant children integration identified by research areas described in tasks 1.3, 1.4 and 1.5

Table 3. Summary of the outcomes identified in the qualitative research

OUTCOMES IN RESEARCH ON PSYCHOSOCIAL WELLBEING	OUTCOMES IN RESEARCH ON INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCES AND MULTILINGUALISM	OUTCOMES IN RESEARCH ON GENDER
Sense of belonging	Cultural capital (exposure and coping) that serve the individual as a personal resource in a multicultural environment.	Behaviour
Confidence/self-esteem (inc. sense of hope/future orientation)	Social bridges with native peers and supporting bonds with the family, teachers and peers	Peer attachment
Happiness	Inclusive social climate	Familial gender roles
Sense of identity	Intercultural identity in which they adopt the cultural features of the host society according to their personal values without renounce to their cultural heritage.	Familial values
Knowledge and retention of home language	Sense of belonging in the host society.	Religious beliefs
Acquisition of host language	Positive expectations towards the future and the school.	Teacher-peer attachment
Friendships (within and outside of school)	Skills to manage realistically their own expectation and the expectations that others place on them	Gender stereotypes
Good relationships with teachers	Skills to manage and resolve conflicts (i.e. intercultural dialogue, avoiding risk...)	Gender bias
Academic achievement	Isolating in intra-ethnic or same linguistic background communities	Educational expectations
<i>De jure</i> and <i>de facto</i> access to education	Negative attitudes, caution and distrust towards native people and institutions	Student performance
		Shifts in gender roles
		Cultural dissonance

By this point, qualitative research on the three thematic areas provided several individual and situational factors that affected the achievement of a successful integration, which were identified and clustered by topics. The presence of the determinants in the different ecological levels was codified and quantified when identified in each country (0=not identified in any country 6=identified in the six countries), representing cross-country barriers and facilitators experienced in the European contexts:

Table 4. Summary of the determinants identified in the qualitative research

DETERMINANTS CLUSTERS	PRESENCE BY LEVELS			PRESENCE TOTAL
	MICRO	MESO	MACRO	
Negative attitudes	6	6	6	6
Family culture	6	6	6	6
Individual/familiar structural features	6	4	4	6
School organization & teachers	0	5	4	5
Dispositional individual features	5	3	2	5
Learning support	2	4	4	4
Political leadership	0	4	4	4
Allocation of students	0	3	4	4
Migration circumstances	4	4	4	4
Ethnic/linguistic/cultural points of support	2	3	2	3
School segregation	0	2	3	3
Mental health services	0	1	2	2
Foreign languages at school	0	0	2	2

The findings of the workshops were highly aligned with those of the literature review, but did help to refine the final proposed parameters and contents of the dashboard in the following manner:

- In terms of parameters, the workshops and consultations highlighted the school and the neighbourhood, as well as relevant policy-making at the regional and national level, as key and strategic spheres of intervention. The literature widely supports this view, although emphasizing the determinant role of parents and family environment in the final outcomes of children, and particularly in mediating the impact of the school. However, child and family factors can only be indirectly influenced by policy intervention, which by definition can be designed and implemented only at higher levels (school, neighbourhood, policy-making). Following the policy relevance and efficiency criteria, then, IMMERSE will focus on the latter spheres (meso and macro levels) to select the facilitators and barriers included in the dashboard. This means the dashboard will observe the variation and evolution in these areas of intervention, monitor their impact and provide relevant recommendations. This does not mean that the role of family or individual child factors will be ignored. First, many of the relevant meso and macro factors considered are directed towards having an impact on those factors (e.g. increasing parent involvement at school). Second, IMMERSE will prioritize indicators and collect data that can be disaggregated by individual and family-level factors, so that the relevant empirical controls can be included and relevant conclusions on these factors can also be considered.
- In terms of contents, the 5 identified outcome dimensions clearly emerged across contexts and types of stakeholders in the workshops and consultations. Very importantly, the workshop findings emphasized particular aspects of these dimensions: for instance, the key role of social relations (and in particular with peers at school) for the wellbeing of children and therefore for their successful integration. Most of the barriers and facilitators identified by the literature also similarly emerged during the workshops, but consistently emphasizing some of them as key and strategic across contexts, such as the clear leadership by policy-makers and school management teams in fostering appreciation of diversity and intercultural dialogue. These findings reaffirmed the mapping of outcomes and barriers and facilitators delineated in the Conceptual Framework, but also helped us prioritize particular contents for the dashboard.

2.3 FINAL SELECTION OF CONTENTS AND PARAMETERS

Taking into account the Conceptual Framework and the workshops findings, a final overall proposal was prepared regarding both the parameters and the contents of the dashboard, which we summarize below.

2.3.1 Parameters of the dashboard

The dashboard will be composed of two types of contents (i.e. factors):

- **Outcomes** consist of children's results that are considered key in assessing or evaluating their integration (i.e. in terms of reaching their full potential and become fully recognized

members of society at the formal and informal levels) according to the literature and the relevant stakeholders. These outcomes belong to 5 key dimensions (access to rights, language and culture, well-being, connectedness and educational achievements), for which we have identified 8 key subdimensions conformed by 16 factors. These factors and dimensions would constitute the main components of the integration process, i.e. they should allow us to approximate the latent variable of “integration”.

Figure 1. Outcomes of the integration process of migrant-background children

- Barriers and facilitators** are meso and macro level determinants of the selected outcomes. These are key spheres of intervention susceptible of policy recommendations in order to foster the integration process at both the macro and meso levels, and including them in the dashboard will allow assessing variations in key policy/programs and monitoring their evolution. A total of 66 such factors were identified, which are detailed in Annex 1, and which we group into four main categories:

- School factors: those circumscribed to the school
- Neighbourhood factors: those circumscribed to the neighbourhood (which can also include the school)
- Macro factors: these are mostly composed of public policies and resources (at the regional or national level), which we have grouped under two sub-categories:
 - o LPC = “Legislation and practice conditioning” access to different rights (e.g. LPC access to compulsory education)
 - o LRR = “Legislation, recommendations and resources” that frame, limit and condition relevant aspects of the meso level (e.g. school programming, attention services at the neighbourhood level). Each “LRR” largely corresponds to similar/equivalent determinants at the meso level (i.e. at schools and neighbourhoods). The key level for observation and intervention (e.g. whether school implementation, regional legislation and resources, or national ones) might vary by country, depending on the level of school autonomy, and regional-national competences.
- Multi-level factors: these are factors (i.e. experience or perception of negative attitudes, and experience of harassment or physical violence) that are relevant at all levels of observation (school, neighbourhood, public opinion and media), so we might consider all levels or select some of them (e.g. presence of conflict in terms of bullying at schools or/and generally episodes of discrimination and/or hate speech or hate episodes at local, regional or national levels).

Taking into consideration the multi-dimensionality of the object of research, it is necessary to specify the main **levels of observation and analysis** of the dashboard contents. On the one hand, the outcomes are defined at the micro level (children outcomes) but they will be aggregated at the meso level (children outcomes at the school, neighbourhood and local level) as well as at the macro level (children outcomes at regional and/or national level). On the other hand, the barriers and facilitators of the meso and macro levels will be observed at the corresponding levels (school, neighbourhood, regional and national levels) and successively aggregated at higher levels when required.

The information included in the dashboard will be complemented by additional information necessary to disaggregate, modulate and interpret the data, which we generally refer to as “**variables of disaggregation**”. The role of these variables can be explained from two points of view: from the point of view of an indicator system monitoring public policy and outcomes, they provide the context and inputs upon which interventions act and have effect or not; from the point of view of statistical analysis, these variables amount to control variables - while outcomes are the dependent variables (measuring the latent variable of “integration”) and determinants (barriers and facilitators) are independent or explaining variables. In the case of IMMERSE dashboard, the variables of disaggregation are important determinants of the selected outcomes (i.e. they are known to impact them) but are not part of the selected outcomes and barriers and facilitators. Still, they must be taken into consideration to interpret the information in the dashboard. There are two main types:

- Child and family characteristics (like age, sex or time since arrival, but also others like mother tongue, country of origin or socio-economic status) are considered as “inputs” into the integration process for the reasons discussed above – they can only be indirectly influenced by policy intervention, which by definition can be designed and implemented only at higher levels (school, neighbourhood, policy-making. It is important to note, then, that many of these factors are indeed affected by policies. For instance, personal resilience or parental involvement with schools can be improved and programs could be dedicated to this, and basic characteristics like countries of origin have to do with long-term policies regulating migration flows. So these factors are not merely inputs but are partly the product of (and subject to) intervention. Nonetheless, since intervention can only be indirect in this sphere, and according to the defined parameters of the dashboard, they are not included as indicators, but as key information to be collected and considered in the interpretation of the results.
- School and neighbourhood characteristics (like rate of migrant-background students or residents, rural-urban habitat, private-public ownership, or socio-economic status of residents or students) are key sources of variation for the units of analysis at the meso level, and as such must be included in the sampling strategy to reflect and control for the heterogeneity of meso contexts across Europe. For this reason, these characteristics will be considered as a “given” for the units of analysis at the meso level, even though their levels and distribution can be clearly affected by policies. For instance, the rate of migrant background students can be impacted by policies tackling segregation.

2.3.2 Preselection of contents (factors) of the dashboard

The designed objective of the IMMERSE is a dashboard of only 30 indicators that should allow measuring and monitoring the integration of migrant-background children. The starting point for this final selection was designed to be a pre-selection of 50 factors, for which empirical indicators would be selected next and submitted for evaluation to experts and stakeholders. The basis for this pre-selection was the mapping conducted and discussed above, which had identified 16 key outcomes (grouped under the 5 dimensions and 8 sub-dimensions) and 66 barriers and facilitators at the meso and macro levels, following the literature review and workshop findings (see Annex 1). In total, 82 factors from which only 50 had to be preselected.

The preselection had to include all 16 outcomes identified, since these were the cornerstone of the model emerging from the literature and workshops findings in terms of defining the latent variable of integration, and its related determinants. In order to reach the figure of 50 factors, then, we focused on the preselection of 34 among the 66 meso and macro determinants identified. With this aim, each country team in the IMMERSE consortium, relying on their specific expertise and on the insights gained in their local workshops, conducted an initial preselection of such 34 factors. The aim was to ensure the relevance of the final preselection for all the contexts considered. Each team based and justified their selection on the basis of their Adequacy (importance for measuring and monitoring the integration process of children) and/or Relevance (importance for and feasibility of intervention at the meso and macro levels in their specific context). Relying once again on the

robustness criterion, we based the final overall preselection on those factors gathering the largest consensus across country teams. In total, 21 factors added up between 3-4 votes and 21 other factors were selected by at least two teams. These highest-placed 42 factors were then analysed in order to ensure their adequacy and relevance. On the one hand, these 42 factors included all the factors that had emerged in all or most of the country workshops according to partners' feedback, certifying a proper incorporation of the co-creation pillar. Similarly, 30 of these 42 factors were identified by several country teams as priority areas for intervention based in their particular contexts. The 43th factor of the primary ranking (corresponding to school segregation by socio-economic status) gathered a significant consensus on its policy relevance at both meso and macro levels, and for that reason it was added to the final selection (see Annex 2 for final ranking and selection).

The additional criteria of **efficiency and feasibility**¹² were then considered, together with the requirement of ensuring a **balanced presence** of all key outcomes (i.e. sufficient representation of key determinants for each of them). In this case, a more qualitative approach was adopted. We grouped together all determinants related to one very same factor/topic (a total of 9 clusters) in order to analyse how that particular topic was being covered. This cluster-approach ensured a proper equilibrium of the general topics identified as key determinants for our outcomes, while allowing a more refined intra-cluster selection of key factors. We considered the relations between different factors and across different levels in each cluster, including: (1) whether some of them included or approximated enough some of the others, (2) whether some of them had feasibility issues, and (3) how efficient they were in terms of types and number of outcomes impacted. A total of 9 factors were identified as additional candidates to be dropped (see Annex 3 for clusters and final drops). This already provided the exact number of determinants we were looking for, so no further selection was needed. We confirmed also the balanced nature of the selection at the global level of the dashboard: the resulting selection included 17 meso-level indicators (15 school, 2 neighbourhood), 16 macro-level indicators, and 2 that are multi-level (attitudes can be observed at meso and/or macro level). The selection also included a sufficient number of key determinants for each of the 5 outcomes dimensions, proportional to the overall number of key determinants identified by the literature. This means that the legal dimension had the lowest number of determinants, mostly concentrated on the legal frameworks that provide access to different legal statuses and to specific rights.

3 SELECTION AND REFINEMENT OF EMPIRICAL INDICATORS

The IMMERSE team developed a proposal of empirical indicators to operationalize the pre-selected 50 factors, that is, to empirically observe and measure the latent variable of migrant children's integration, as well as their main barriers and facilitators. This proposal was based on a mapping exercise of already existing indicators, and an effort to develop some original ones where needed.

¹² The feasibility criterion refers to whether information exists or can be collected, and how efficiently, i.e. whether is already available, whether there are practical issues for collecting the data, for instance from small children and parents; etc.

The proposed factors and empirical indicators were then subjected to content and ecological validation. First, they were **content validated** and evaluated by a group of international experts using a DELPHI methodology. Based on this evaluation, the 30 indicators intended to compose the dashboard were to be selected and refined. Next, the resulting indicators were subjected to **ecological validation** at the micro, meso and macro levels through online consultations and face-to-face workshops with the relevant stakeholders. This evaluation and selection process, again involving an academic and a co-creation pillar, was intended to ensure the validity and relevance of the selected dashboard of indicators. The goal was to obtain an evaluation system for migrant children's socio-educational integration that serves stakeholders' needs (including those of children) and that is useful not only for academic research, but also, and in particular, for policy-making evaluation and guidance. The main stages and the final results of this process are detailed below.

3.1 PRE-SELECTION OF 50 INDICATORS

3.1.1 Mapping: catalogue of indicators

As discussed in Section 2.2., the selection of the empirical indicators was to be based on the criteria of robustness and efficiency. First, the empirical indicators selected to measure the outcomes and determinants must concite consensus about their validity and empirical robustness, both among experts and among the consulted stakeholders. Second, they should be, preferably, already available and produced in a regular and sustainable manner by reliable and trusted sources in all relevant countries. Based on these criteria, we conducted a mapping exercise of indicators that are already available from well-established secondary sources, covering all six IMMENSE countries, and producing or collecting data with some regularity. This was based on a thorough review of relevant sources of indicators including quantitative and qualitative data and, more generally, relevant information on refugee and migrants' integration in Europe and on socio-educational inclusion. Over 40 sources were selected and documented. The main sources offering ample information on the key outcomes and determinants identified and that also met the relevant criteria were: Eurostat/Zaragoza indicators; MIPEX;¹³ OECD/PISA; and OECD's Child Wellbeing Database. We also identified relevant specific indicators available from a diversity of sources, including specialized surveys (such as the ESS, EVS, WVS, TALIS, PIRLS, TIMSS, PIAAC) and other OECD and Eurostat statistics. The potentially relevant indicators and data contained in these secondary sources were mapped out. Once the 50 factors were pre-selected as detailed above, the candidate indicators were grouped together in a Catalogue of Indicators that was then further completed with additional and specialized sources, such as surveys on child well-being.

3.1.2 Selection and definition of indicators

The Catalogue of Indicators served as the basis for the initial proposal of indicators that would measure each of the pre-selected 50 factors. Using the Catalogue as a reference, the possible

¹³ The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).

indicators for each selected factors were extensively discussed in a collaborative and multidisciplinary effort by IMMERSE researchers and collaborators in all 6 IMMERSE countries. For each factor:

- The goal was to select one single empirical indicator for each preselected factor. However, two or more indicators had to be selected for factors that were complex or multidimensional in nature. For instance, peer interconnectedness was deemed as a relevant factor in terms of the support it provides to children, but both the existence of such ties and the amount of contact were considered key in measuring it. Additionally, the presence of bridges between children with different backgrounds was also seen a necessary component of successful integration processes, building both on the literature and the workshop findings.
- Indicators that were already available through existing sources were prioritized, but they had then to be deemed adequate and robust by the researchers and for our specific object of research. If several candidates were available, only one was finally selected according to the researchers' evaluation of their adequacy, robustness and feasibility (except in the cases of multiple indicators discussed above).
- Where an adequate indicator already existed in the form of a survey item but the data were not available or the sources did not meet the necessary criteria or coverage, the IMMERSE team opted for reproducing the survey item and/or indicator – when this was possible or permission was granted – and collecting it on our own through the IMMERSE surveys.
- Where no adequate indicator was available or met the desired characteristics, an original indicator was developed by the research team and collaborators. The data used to build the indicator could be data to be collected from dispersed secondary sources (e.g. Ministries data) or (in most cases) through the IMMERSE surveys.

The final list of 50 factors and the indicators proposed for each of them – a total of 57 due to the multi-layered nature of some of the factors – can be found in Annex 5.

3.2 CONTENT VALIDATION AND SELECTION OF 30 INDICATORS

3.2.1 DELPHI methodology

The set of 50 factors (and 57 indicators) was content-validated by a group of 24 top international experts in the areas of education and migration, academia, NGOs and public administration by using an online DELPHI consultation.¹⁴ The final profile composition of the experts group for the DELPHI validation included 10 experts specialised in migration, 9 experts specialised in education and 5 mixed profiles specialised in the effect of migration in socio-educational inclusion. The current dedication of the members of the DELPHI included 13 researchers, 4 advisors with previous experience on migration policy incidence, 2 high representatives of NGOs, 3 advisors in education and 2 advisors with expertise in governance and socio-educational inclusion of migrant children.

¹⁴ The Calibrum software was selected as the means to conduct the online consultation. This software provided an online platform specifically designed to conduct research with Delphi methodology. Classic Delphi methodology is a consensus-oriented group decision-making technique over multiple survey rounds. The expert method allows group members to share and exchange their opinions without undue influence or social drawbacks, and shape them into a decision that is in the best interest of the whole. It has been previously implemented in other research projects to aid strategic foresight decision-making activities all over the world.

The large number of participants, their level of expertise, reputation and specialization, and the heterogeneity of their profiles help ensure the robustness of the DELPHI process.

Table 5. Accumulated frequencies of number of experts by field of expertise

FIELDS OF EXPERTISE (multiple options)	N
Education	17
Migration	12
Public Policy	5
Childhood	5
Mental Health	4
Refugee Studies	4
Education in crisis and post-crisis	1

The DELPHI consists on a methodology of content validation based on the structured discussion from a group of experts that assesses if the qualitative aspects of a construct and the provided operational definition are sufficiently brought into line. The result of the DELPHI validation is a quantitative result obtained by the consensus reached and the later statistical analysis of the experts' responses. In our case, the DELPHI methodology provided a consensus on the key determinants and outcomes in the socio-educational integration of migrant children, starting with the initial list (in English) of the 50 factors / 57 indicators. The consensus was built through two consecutive rounds of consultation. Specifically, each of the indicators was presented in each screen with the name of the factor, the description of the empirical measurement and details about the source, etc. For each indicator, the experts were asked to provide a score on the four CARA dimensions:

- **CLARITY** of the indicator: whether the indicator is drafted in a concrete and non-ambiguous way and it has a single possibility of interpretation. The experts must rate each indicator in a four-value scale from 1 (very low) to 4 (very high clarity).
- **ADEQUACY** of the indicator: whether the indicator is appropriate and it refers to key or highly influential factors to achieve the socio-educational integration of migrant children. The experts must rate each indicator in a four-value scale from 1 (completely disagree) to 4 (completely agree) that the indicator is adequate.
- **RELEVANCE** of the indicator: whether the indicator is important regarding public policies or for educational centres to accomplish their mission of socio-educational integration of migrant children. The experts must rate each indicator in a four-value scale from 1 (not important at all) to 4 (very important).
- **ACCESSIBILITY** of the indicator: whether there are sources of accessible information that could let us obtain the necessary data to make a reliable indicator measurement. The experts must indicate for each indicator Yes it is available or No it is not available.

The experts could also add volunteer comments for each indicator, and overall comments at the end. At the end of each round, the experts were asked to select the five indicators that, in their opinion, best represented the key factors that are most important to assess the socio-educational integration of migrant children, by order of priority. The first round resulted in **11 indicators reaching a positive consensus among experts**, meaning that at least 60% of the experts picked the same

(positive) value on all 4 CARA dimensions. In the second consultation round, these 11 indicators were eliminated, and the experts were asked to re-assess the list of remaining 46 indicators that had not reached consensus. In this new round, the experts had access to the other experts' comments and ratings for each indicator, and they could change their assessments and comments. This second round resulted in **5 more indicators reaching consensus**.¹⁵ The high profile of the participating international experts was matched with a highly committed response by most of them in terms of providing substantial comments (which were optional and not explicitly requested from them) and intensively engaging with the 1st and 2nd round mechanics, meaning that most experts not only participated in the 2nd round but also modified their inputs based on the reflections of other experts in the 1st round, as well as engaging in a feedback dialogue in their comments.

3.2.2 DELPHI analysis

Since only 16 indicators reached consensus, a further analysis of the DELPHI results was necessary to establish the final selection of 30 indicators. Moreover, we intended to select 5 additional ones, in order to ensure that a minimum of 30 validated indicators would remain in case some might be dropped in the final ecological validation. The final selection of these 30 plus 5 indicators was based on the quantitative analysis of the results of the DELPHI, and guided and refined by a qualitative analysis of the comments provided by the experts.

First, a primary ranking of indicators was built based on the average score (across experts in the 2nd round) in the Adequacy and Relevance categories. These are the CARA categories that determine the relative importance for inclusion in the dashboard, according to the experts. A total of 31 indicators had a score above average. We also built another primary ranking based on the average score across all four CARA categories, denoting indicators that also scored well in Clarity and Accessibility. A total of 32 indicators had a score above 3. The overlap between both rankings is substantial: 30 indicators met both benchmarks. Second, to improve the robustness of the results, we considered two additional quality criteria that denoted experts' consensus and overall prioritisation: (1) indicators picked by more than a quarter of the experts as part of their top-5 selection; (2) indicators that received the maximum value in Adequacy or in Relevance from 60% of the experts or more.

Next, we analysed the experts' qualitative comments on every single indicator from different points of view: reliability of answers, potential for misinterpretation, empirical evidence on the indicator's behaviour, etc. For each indicator, we identified the aspects (positive or negative) where clear or wide consensus emerged in the comments, and also singled out comments pointing at serious limitations or positive qualities of the indicator by the most qualified experts (i.e. those who were the most specialized on the particular topic or measurement, or highly familiarized with the original sources, as in the case of MIPEX). In some cases the qualitative comments were considered

¹⁵ Each consultation round involved a time commitment of one to two hours depending on the time that the expert dedicated to each indicator's response (although it was suggested to spend no more than 2-3 minutes per indicator) and requested consent provision. A total of 24 experts participated and completed the two DELPHI rounds and 23 of them provided comments about qualitative aspects of the indicators.

important enough as to overcome the quantitative rankings and consensus reached (more details below). It is important to keep in mind that the qualitative comments – unlike the overall quantitative assessment provided by each expert – allowed distinguishing between the two levels of selection involved in the exercise, that is, the factor that we aimed to measure, on the one hand, and the empirical measurement that was proposed with that aim, on the other hand.

3.2.3 DELPHI results

We classified the 57 indicators into four groups that helped us prioritize their selection.

- GROUP A included 12 indicators that were in the upper part of the primary rankings and also displayed some of the additional quality criteria. These were automatically selected for inclusion in the dashboard.
- GROUP B included 19 indicators from the upper part of the primary rankings that did not display any of the additional quality criteria. These indicators were second-prioritised for inclusion in the dashboard. Together with Group A, they added up 31 indicators.
- GROUP C included the 9 indicators that followed those in group A and B in the primary rankings, most of which also displayed additional quality criteria, adding up a pool of 40 indicators for the final selection.
- GROUP D included the 17 indicators at the bottom of the primary rankings and were *a priori* discarded.

Group by group, we proceeded to consider the experts' qualitative comments for each indicator. Based on the insight gained from these comments, all indicators were improved by introducing further points of clarification and information. In some cases, additional refinements and improvements were introduced following the experts' suggestions, which we discuss below. The suggestions led sometimes to a change in the survey items used as a basis for the indicator.¹⁶ Finally, indicators for which the experts raised significant concerns were dropped in those cases where no clear solutions or alternatives were suggested or found. We turned consecutively to groups C and D to complete the selection. Below we detail this decision-making process and the main decisions taken.

GROUP A

No issues of concern were identified for these 12 indicators, but the experts did provide some suggestions to help improve some of them. Three indicators were refined following qualified indications by the experts,¹⁷ and four other indicators were more significantly modified following well-qualified comments or robust consensus among the experts.

¹⁶ Those modified survey items to be collected from children were discussed with the CRAG in a dedicated workshop before their final selection to cross-check the new development.

¹⁷ These included: using the difference between native and migrant-background children instead of an absolute measure of the latter in a couple of indicators, and using a meso and macro level aggregate for attitudes towards migration (D6.1).

- First, and as a general comment for all the proposed indicators from MIPEX,¹⁸ we were advised to utilize the more aggregate categories (dimensions, policy strands and overall score) instead of specific individual indicators, in order to increase the robustness of the measurement. The selected indicators for factor D4.15.5 (LRR Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally) belong to a broader MIPEX dimension ("Intercultural Education For All"), which also includes other MIPEX indicators preselected in groups B and C.¹⁹ By resorting to the score in this wider dimension, the factor itself becomes broader and has been recast as "LRR Intercultural education", reabsorbing said factors from groups B and C.
- Second, the survey item used to capture O2.1.1 (Children's competence in host language) was substituted by another formulation following the recommendations of the experts, in order to capture linguistic competence in a more straightforward manner, paying attention to the social and academic dimensions of communication at school.
- The experts also made us reconsider factor D3.7.1 (Disadvantaged schools by socio-economic status of students attending), which aimed to capture the concentration of students of low socio-economic status at school level. We recast it into a factor and indicator aimed at capturing the differential presence of migrant-background children in socio-economically disadvantaged schools instead. The nuance is important because it captures the link between socio-economically disadvantaged centres – the most important determinant of educational outcomes at school level – and concentration of migrant-background children in such centres. Thus, the observation of this link will be direct and straightforward.
- Finally, the proposed indicator for factor D3.2.1 (Clear leadership and school identity around intercultural values, against xenophobia, prejudice and stereotypes – which has robustly emerged as a top factor to consider in all the phases of assessment, including literature review, workshops, and the quantitative and qualitative results of this DELPHI phase) was seriously qualified by the experts, who considered the survey item employed to be somewhat unclear, too vague to obtain reliable and honest answers from the schools, as well as to be open to opposing dynamics in the direction of the answers. Following these concerns, a new survey item, more objective and straightforward was developed, and the indicator will be based on the answers of both principals and teachers for further robustness and consistency checks.

¹⁸ The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions and policy areas (Strands).

¹⁹ D3.3.1 Training and support resources on intercultural competences and D3.2.2 Incorporation of multiple languages, cultural expressions, cultural dialogue and exchange in school activities

GROUP B

The majority of indicators in this group (10 out of 19) raised no issues of concern but received suggestions for improvement that have been incorporated.²⁰ For the indicator on the *experience* of bullying (D6.1) in particular, the experts made us pay attention to the wording of the question in each particular translation and context (even avoiding the term “bullying” if needed) in order to ensure a common understanding across children and contexts of what is a fuzzy concept.²¹

Two indicators of this group were substantially modified following the experts’ suggestions:

- First, the survey item used for factor D3.4.5 (Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally) raised generalized concern about its vagueness and about the reliability of answers by principals, as well as well-qualified comments on the necessary distinction between curricular and non-curricular approaches. Following these concerns and related suggestions, a new indicator was developed: based on two survey items on the teaching of specific contents at the level of the curriculum (to be asked to principals) and at the level of class teaching (to be asked to teachers).
- Further, it was brought our attention that the MIPEX policy dimension “Anti-discrimination” selected to capture factor D4.7 (Clear and effective leadership - regional and national- on intercultural values, against xenophobia, prejudice and stereotypes) was strongly affected by the highly context-specific and formal anti-discrimination laws in Eastern European countries, foreseen specifically for tackling discrimination of national and ethnic minorities in these countries.²² We were advised to use instead the MIPEX overall policy score, which has proved a robust indicator of the intended type of leadership,²³ as it takes into account multiple areas of policy making and multiple possible approaches for dealing with xenophobia or discrimination, both at the institutional and social levels, thus capturing the more direct and indirect effects exercised by political leadership. It is important to note that the MIPEX overall policy score includes dimensions and strands that are used elsewhere in other selected indicators. We aimed to avoid this type of empirical overlap among the factors and indicators selected, but the empirical argument for the use of the overall policy

²⁰ These include: using the difference between native and migrant-background children instead of an absolute measure of the latter in several indicators; combining macro and meso observations for the existence of provisions and level of implementation of preparatory classes (D4.16.1); duplicating survey items to capture the offer of extra-curricular learning and language support also at schools, not only in the neighbourhood (D5.6); and considering the answers of both teachers and students about teachers’ low expectations (D3.3.3). In some cases the suggestions also helped refine the survey items to be used in the data collection. These included: following up questions on the *experience* of bullying and fear of places by a question on the alleged reasons for these situations (D6.1 and D6.2); widening and clarifying the definition of groups on which teachers may have lower expectations (D3.3.3); expanding the considered dimensions of teachers’ support (O4.1.2); and narrowing the list of institutions in the institutional trust question in order to make it clearer for children and subsequent interpretation (O4.1.3).

²¹ According to the Council of Europe: “Bullying is unwanted, aggressive behaviour among school-aged children that involves a real or perceived power imbalance. The behaviour is repeated, or has the potential to be repeated, over time.” (<https://www.coe.int/en/web/children/bullying>, accessed 10 February 2020). In other words, the concept of bullying is built around three dimensions (aggressive behaviour, repetition and power imbalance) that have porous limits and potentially different interpretations on those limits.

²² See research pieces by Conrad Ziller (Ziller, 2014; Ziller & Helbling, 2019)

²³ Several multi-level analyses have found that MIPEX overall score is the only contextual factor with a strong effect on public opinion (Bilgili, Huddleston, & Joki, 2015; Niessen & Huddleston, 2009; Ziller, 2014)

score is also consistent with the analytical and theoretical basis of the conceptual framework and this factor in particular. Namely, all policy dimensions measured in the macro determinants contribute to characterizing this type of political leadership, although each of them in specific areas with some direct impact on children's outcomes. However, having a clear leadership that upholds intercultural values has a specific weight of its own,²⁴ and such leadership is characterized by the addition of all those multiple areas of policy making under several multiple approaches. In other words, factor D4.7 represents an encompassing category of a higher hierarchical order, whereas other policy factors (LPC and LRR) are specific instances, of special interest, within that dimension of political leadership.²⁵

Two other indicators were ultimately dropped from the final selection following the concerns expressed by the experts and a lack of clear alternatives:

- First, the indicator for factor D3.5.2 (Learning and language support), based on the existence of staff hired to provide learning support for different needs, was found problematic for several reasons: it led to mixing special needs with different types of diversity, and language and curriculum support; the experts considered necessary to contextualize it with information about size and diversity of the school, requiring further and complex data collection; and most importantly, the indicator was found to have multiple and contradictory interpretations, since sometimes support staff is hired when there is a more serious issue of ratios and personnel scarcity, meaning larger numbers could have a positive or negative interpretation depending on the background context. The indicator (and factor) was dropped in view of these concerns and given that no specific suggestions for a new type of indicator were provided.
- Second, the indicator for factor D6.2 (Experience of harassment and/or physical violence outside family) based on the *exercise* of bullying on other children was considered highly interesting and relevant by most experts, and it actually reached consensus in the first round.²⁶ However, a number of experts raised concerns about the low reliability of the answers: first, as a matter of honesty among respondents; and second, as a matter of lack of clarity on how bullying is understood from the perspective of participants or potential perpetrators. While measurement issues exist for the *experience* of bullying (as discussed above) they might be exacerbated when measuring the *exercise* of bullying, leading to unequal self-assessments and answering dynamics, which might require further contextualization. On top of these concerns, using this data as an indicator risked a potential criminalizing and stigmatizing effect on whichever categories (encompassing both or either migrant-background or native children) which might display a higher rate of positive answers, particularly in the absence of contextualizing information. Having into

²⁴ This is not only documented in the literature, but also robustly emerged as a top factor during the workshops.

²⁵ This relationship will have to be taken into account in any empirical analysis that considers all or several indicators of the dashboard, excluding the factors with collinearity, and it will be made part of the methodological caveats.

²⁶ The consensus was among the weakest obtained, though: only 60% in Adequacy and Clarity (i.e. barely reaching the minimum threshold) and only 63% in Relevance. For reference, most indicators reaching consensus obtained at least 65%-70% consensus in at least two of these key criteria.

account that the traditional question on *experience* of bullying was already selected, this more problematic indicator was decided to be dropped.

Group B also included 6 factors proxied by MIPEX indicators. Following the advice to resort to more aggregate MIPEX categories, further merges and reorganization of these factors were decided.

- First, the selected indicators for factor D4.3 (LPC access to compulsory education) and D4.19.1 (LRR Criteria for incorporation to educational levels upon arrival), belong to the broader MIPEX dimension ("Access to Education "). Both factors were then recast into a broader one (LPC access to education) proxied by the score in that MIPEX dimension.²⁷
- The same solution was applied to the factors D4.16.2 and D4.16.3 (LRR Language and learning support within/outside mainstream classes, and at alternative environments, respectively), now recast into the broader "LRR Educational support for migrant children", proxied by the MIPEX dimension "Targeting needs".
- Finally, factor D3.3.1 (Training and support resources on intercultural competences) was absorbed into the recast factor D4.15.5 (LRR Intercultural education) discussed above in Group A.

At this point, taking into account the MIPEX merges and indicators dropped, only 26 indicators were selected between groups A and B. Nine more indicators were needed to reach the established goal of 30 plus 5 additional indicators. We turned then to the 9 indicators that followed group A and B in the overall results of the DELPHI (group C).

GROUP C

Four of these 9 indicators raised no issues of concern but received suggestions for improvement that have been incorporated.²⁸ Among these indicators, we switched the standard NEET indicator (young people neither working nor studying) for the standard early-leavers indicator (O5.2.2) after taking into consideration the experts' comments on these two closely related indicators, both of which we had similarly very closely considered for inclusion in the initial preselection.

One more indicator was substantially modified following the experts' suggestions:

- The survey item used for factor D3.2.3 (School promotion of parental involvement in school activities. extra-curricular activities and parental associations) raised concerns about its vagueness and multiple possible interpretations, both in terms of level of implementation and effective mechanisms to be considered. Some experts also emphasized the importance of capturing the specific barriers for and interactions between the participation of migrant-background parents and native parents. Following these suggestions, we developed a survey item asking principals about the use of some specific channels of

²⁷ This dimension also also evaluates legal and effective access to other levels of education (non-compulsory, vocational, higher education), making a wider assessment of access to educational rights, although with a particular weight for compulsory education..

²⁸ These include: using the difference between native and migrant-background children instead of an absolute measure of the latter in several indicators; duplicating survey items to capture different sources of diversity in peers networks (O4.1.1) and refining reference categories (O2.2.2).

participation, and whether these were adapted to specific needs such as language and culture. Additionally, we will also collect information on participation from the parents.

Three other indicators were ultimately dropped:

- The indicator on D4.12 (LRR early education), which was defined as rates of participation in early education, was seen by most experts as subject to multiple interpretations, as participation is influenced by many factors other than policy. Experts also considered these data are difficult to obtain, but no convincing alternatives were found or provided for a different indicator.
- Next, the indicator on D4.15.1 (Bilingualism - instruction in 2 languages) received exclusively negative comments. Some pointed out to the diverse situations and contexts that the indicator covers – from regional dialects to multiple national languages and additional foreign languages. Others pointed out that, in a majority of countries and regions, bilingual education is not available for an immense majority of the migrant-children population, making it a less relevant factor and indicator.
- Finally, the indicator on D5.2.1 (Presence of ethnic/cultural/migrant networks and communities) was generally disliked for several reasons, most importantly, not being a proper measure of networks and not focusing on ethnic or cultural minorities. The indicator was ultimately dropped because the information (presence of migrant-background population) will be collected in any case and it is more appropriately to be considered as a disaggregation variable.

One more factor from this group (D3.2.2 Incorporation of multiple languages, cultural expressions, cultural dialogue and exchange in school activities) was proxied by MIPEx indicators that had been absorbed in the previous merges (LRR Intercultural Education). This left us with 30 plus 1 additional indicators selected, still short of 4 additional ones, for which we turned to Group D.

Group D

In order to select 4 out of the 18 initially discarded indicators, we proceeded by order of score in the quantitative results of the DELPHI, checking whether the qualitative comments allowed for refinements in the indicators that would further support their reconsideration. Following this criterion, four indicators were discarded again because of the issues raised in the qualitative comments and the lack of clear alternatives. The final four indicators recovered were the following:

- The indicator on D3.6.2 (Counselling and therapeutic services at school) was based on a survey item that raised concerns among experts regarding its vague wording. Building on the suggestions provided, we decided to substitute it for a survey item on school staff dedicated to psycho-social support or personal counselling.
- The indicator on D4.2 (LPC acquisition of superior legal status) was considered next. We were particularly happy to reconsider this factor, as it is a cornerstone of the conceptual framework and, until this point, none of the legal status outcomes and none of their key determinants had made it to the final selection. One main suggestion and one main criticism were raised by the experts. First, we were advised to use the full MIPEx strand on

Access to Nationality, rather than using only two of its dimensions. Second, the criticisms pointed out to the incomplete nature of the indicator, since it focused only on citizenship and not on other relevant status acquisitions, such as regular status or humanitarian protection – although some of the experts supported the selection of citizenship as a key criterion for formal participation and membership of society.²⁹ In order to address these concerns, we attempted to include additional indicators for these other legal transitions inasmuch they offer a more complete picture of the legal paths towards status improvement and stabilization. Unfortunately, no viable indicators are available, to our knowledge, for the transition from irregular to regular status. But taking into account that one major impact (on children’s wellbeing) of this type of transition is related to the security of status – which frequently it is not fully ensured when regularizing for the first time – we opted instead for the MIPEX policy strand on Access to Permanent Residence as a second indicator on D4.2. As for the acquisition of refugee status, since no similar policy indicator was available,³⁰ we opted for a relative measure of yearly positive decisions on children as a third indicator of D4.2. As noted by some experts, this type of indicator is affected by factors other than policy, such as flow arrivals and willingness to seek asylum, which should be taken into consideration, but to some extent these are also mediated by policy components similar to those measured in the other two indicators.³¹

These final inclusions added up a total of 30 plus 5 indicators,³² which were submitted then to the stakeholders for their ecological validation. The overall balance in terms of outcomes and determinants for the 30 plus 5 indicators are summarized in the tables below. All the key outcome dimensions and their main subdimensions are represented in the selection, with the exception of O1.1 (Legal status), O2.2.1 (Children's competence in mother tongue) and O3.1.1 (Children's self-esteem). Nonetheless, 4, 9 and 19 key determinants for each of these outcomes, respectively, are included, which should help ensure a correct balance for capturing the latent variable of integration.

Table 6. Dashboard of 30+5 indicators

OUTCOMES DIMENSIONS & SUBDIMENSIONS				OUTCOME INDICATORS	DETERMINANTS
O1. Outcomes in access to rights	O1.1 Legal status	O1.1.1 Children's legal status		0	4
	O1.2 Access to rights	O1.2.1 Access to compulsory education		1	3
		O1.2.2 Access to health care		1	3

²⁹ Other criticisms focused on the factor itself (acquisition of superior legal statuses), emphasizing instead the non-formal dimension of membership, i.e. being accepted by society. As discussed in the conceptual framework, we consider both dimensions as necessary components of the integration process, and the preselection aimed to reflect these two components through the different factors and indicators overall.

³⁰ The development of a similar index was on its early stages at the moment of this preselection under the NIEM project: <http://www.forintegration.eu/pl/about-the-project>.

³¹ This type of indicator can also register fluctuations from one year to the next that may have to do with, for instance, administrative backlogs and specific moments where dedicated efforts are put in place, but to some extent this is also a reflection of policy implementation that is relevant to capture, although it may lead to some noise and instability in the yearly series (which might be empirically addressed).

³² 36 if we consider the macro and meso levels of the negative attitudes indicator D6.1

02. Outcomes in language & culture	02.1 Host language	02.1.1 Children's competence in host language		1	10
	02.2 Interculturalism	02.2.1 Children's competence in mother tongue		0	9
		02.2.2 Children maintain their cultural identity while adopting new cultural values and intercultural competences	A.Identity B.Values C.Competences	1	15
03. Outcomes in well-being	03.1 Subjective well-being	03.1.1 Children's self-esteem		0	19
		03.1.2 Children's life satisfaction / happiness		1	18
		03.1.3 Children's sense of belonging		1	19
04. Outcomes in connectedness	04.1 Interconnectedness	04.1.1 Friends and peers	A.Support B.Out school C.Bridges	2	11
		04.1.2 Teachers		1	10
		04.1.3 Institutions		1	11
05. Outcomes in educational achievements	05.1 Academic skills	05.1.1 Children's academic skills		1	16
	05.2 Levels and types of education attained	05.2.1 Children complete compulsory education		1	16
		05.2.2 Children's access formal post-compulsory education		1	16
		05.2.3 Types & levels of formal non-compulsory education attended		1	16

Note: cross-out factors are the ones discarded in this DELPHI phase

A total of 12 meso-level determinants and 10 macro-level determinants are included in the selection:

- Most of the 10 macro-level determinants belong to the political leadership cluster (composed of clear and effective leadership plus policies conditioning access to basic rights – or LPC), besides three LRR indicators for educational support (including language and learning support), intercultural education and preparatory classes. This is complemented by one indicator of negative attitudes at the national level.

The 12 meso-level determinants are concentrated on the clusters of school organization (4), negative attitudes at the local level (3) and supplementary services for learning support and extra-curricular activities at the neighbourhood level (2). Singular indicators have been

selected for the clusters of school segregation, counselling services and ethnic/cultural points of support (at school level in all cases).

Table 7. Dashboard of determinant indicators: clusters of barriers and facilitators

BARRIERS AND FACILITATORS				
CLUSTER	DETERMINANT	FACTOR	MESO	MACRO
POLITICAL LEADERSHIP	D4.7 Clear and effective leadership (regional and national) on intercultural values, against xenophobia, prejudice and stereotypes		0	6
	D4.2 LPC acquisition of superior legal status			
	D4.3 LPC access to education			
	D4.12 LPC / LRR early education			
	D4.6 LPC / LRR Scholarships and benefits available			
	D4.8 LPC access to health care			
	D4.9 LPC access to other basic rights (e.g. housing, benefits...)	A. Housing B. Social protection		
	D4.10 LRR resources (legal assistance, social workers, etc.)			
	D5.1 Available resources (legal assistance, social workers)			
SCHOOL SEGREGATION	D3.7.1 Concentration levels in disadvantaged schools		1	0
	D3.7.2 By Presence of diversity (migrant background, ethnicity, languages; disabilities and learning difficulties)			
SCHOOL ORGANIZATION & TEACHERS	D3.2.1 Clear leadership and school identity around intercultural values, against xenophobia, prejudice and stereotypes		4	1
	D3.2.2 Incorporation of multiple languages, cultural expressions, cultural dialogue and exchange in school activities			
	D3.2.3 School promotion of parental involvement in school activities, extra-curricular activities and parental associations			
	D3.3.1 Training and support resources on intercultural competences			
	D3.4.5 Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally			
	D4.15.5 LRR Intercultural education			
	D3.3.3 Low expectations / stereotypes among teachers towards certain groups			
ALLOCATION OF STUDENTS	D3.8.1 Criteria for incorporation to educational levels upon arrival		0	0
	D4.19.1 LRR Criteria for incorporation to educational levels upon arrival			
LEARNING SUPPORT	D4.16.1 LRR Preparatory classes dedicated/with focus on language acquisition		2	2
	D3.5.2/3 Language/learning support within/outside mainstream classes			

	D4.16.2 LRR Educational support for migrant children, particularly learning and language support			
	D5.5/6 Supplementary community services for language/learning support			
	D4.16.4 LRR Language/learning support at alternative environments			
	D3.5.4 Extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres			
	D4.16.5 LRR Promotion of extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres			
FOREIGN LANGUAGES AT SCHOOL	D4.15.1 Bilingualism (instruction in 2 languages)		0	0
MENTAL HEALTH SERVICES	D3.6.2 Counselling and therapeutic services		1	0
ETHNIC & CULTURAL POINTS OF SUPPORT	D3.1.1 Languages of communication at school			
	D3.3.4 Teachers' diversity		1	0
	D5.2.1 Presence of ethnic/cultural/migrant networks and communities	A.Networks B.Examples		
NEGATIVE ATTITUDES	D6.1 Experience/perception of negative attitudes	A1.Attitudes macro A2.Attitudes meso B.Fear places	3	1
	D6.2 Experience of harassment and/or physical violence outside family	A.Experience B.Participation		
TOTAL			12	10

Note: cross-out factors are the ones eliminated at this stage.

Among the selected indicators, 17 will be based on the re-utilization of secondary data sources and 19 will require the collection of survey data by IMMERSE (there is an overlap in the composite indicator for negative attitudes, which uses both secondary data for the macro level and IMMERSE data for the meso level). Of these, 14 indicators require survey data from children and 7 indicators require survey data from teachers and/or principals.³³

3.3 ECOLOGICAL VALIDATION

The ecological validity of a study implies that the procedures, tools and setting of the research are similar to the real-world under study. Our theoretical framework, structured by Bronfenbrenner’s ecological systems theory, and the co-creation methods followed throughout the whole life of the project support and guarantee the ecological validity of this research. Besides including stakeholders from the micro, meso and macro levels in the earlier phases of the identification of key outcomes and determinants and selection of indicators, we also involved them in the final evaluation of the selected and refined dashboard to ensure its ecological validity. That is, to ensure that the final shape and specification of the selected indicators is valid (i.e. relevant and well-adjusted) from the perspectives of all relevant stakeholders. Children’s inputs are particularly

³³ Survey data from parents will complement 1-2 indicators.

crucial to ecologically validate the micro level indicators due to their two-fold role as subjects and agents of integration.

3.3.1 Meso and macro stakeholders: methodology

The validation with meso and macro-level stakeholders (from the 6 IMMERSE countries: Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy and Spain) was carried out online using Calibrum.³⁴ The stakeholders evaluated in a single round the 30+5 indicators using the CARA criteria once more. The stakeholders could also volunteer qualitative comments for each indicator. This consultation process was carried out with two sub-samples: one at the macro level and one at the meso level.

The macro-level sub-sample was composed of 27 public servants and technicians (local and regional levels) in the areas of education, migration and refugee services and public administration. The sample included 9 male and 17 female participants (one participant preferred not to say), for whom the average years of professional experience was 19.6.

Table 8. Percentage of macro level participants by country

COUNTRY OF ORIGIN	PERCENTAGE
Belgium	22,22%
Greece	22,22%
Spain	22,22%
Ireland	18,52%
Italy	11,11%
Germany	3,70%

Table 9. Percentage of macro level participants by age range

AGE RANGE	PERCENTAGE
18-30	7,41%
31-40	29,63%
41-50	25,93%
51-60	22,22%
61-70	14,81%

Table 10. Percentage of macro level participants by area of professional activity

AREA OF THEIR CURRENT PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY	PERCENTAGE
Education	81,48%
Migration	37,04%
Public Policy Monitoring and Evaluation	33,33%
Childhood	33,33%
Asylum	29,63%
Social Exclusion	25,93%

³⁴ The indicators and the contents of Calibrum were translated into each of the 7 languages of the IMMERSE countries (English, French, Dutch, German, Greek, Italian and Spanish).

Public Policy Design	22,22%
Social Work	11,11%
Mental Health	3,70%

The meso-level sub-sample was composed by 70 members of the educational communities. Their profiles (with possible overlaps) were the following: teachers (78%), principals and managers of educational centres (30%) other members of the educational community (25%). This sample included 18 male and 42 female participants for whom the average years of professional experience was 20.3 years. A majority of participants worked at public schools (75,4%), whereas 18% worked at private schools with subsidized public funds and 6,6% worked at privately owned schools. The average size of these schools was of 1,316 students enrolled.

Table 11. Percentage of meso level participants by country

COUNTRY OF ORIGIN	PERCENTAGE
Spain	29,51%
Greece	18,03%
Belgium	14,75%
Italy	14,75%
Ireland	13,11%
Germany	9,84%

Table 12. Percentage of meso level participants by professional activity

AREA OF CURRENT PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY	PERCENTAGE
Teaching	78,69%
Principal	16,39%
Management	13,11%
Work with youth	11,48%
School mediator	4,92%
Administration	3,28%
External collaborator for school evaluation	3,28%
Parent spokesperson	1,64%
Home School Community Liaison	1,64%
Other	3,28%

Table 13. Percentage of meso level participants by professional activity

EDUCATIONAL LEVELS AT THEIR SCHOOLS OR EDUCATIONAL CENTRES (Multiple answers possible)	PERCENTAGE
Pre-primary (ISCED 0)	4,92%
Primary Education (ISCED 1)	34,43%
Lower secondary education, general (compulsory) (ISCED 2)	42,62%
Lower secondary education, vocational (ISCED 3)	26,23%
Upper secondary education, general (post-compulsory)	45,90%

Leaving Certificate Applied or Leaving Certificate Vocational Programme (ISCED 3)	31,15%
Youth Reach (-)	14,75%

Table 14. Average percentage of meso level participants in relation to the overall number of migrant-background students in their centres

AVERAGE PERCENTAGE OF MIGRANT-BACKGROUND STUDENTS IN RELATION TO THE OVERALL NUMBER OF STUDENTS IN THEIR CENTRES	PERCENTAGE
Less than 10%	24,59%
10-30%	32,79%
30-50%	21,31%
50-70%	8,20%
More than 70%	13,11%

Table 15. Average percentage of meso level participants in relation to the overall number of migrant-background students in their centres

AVERAGE PERCENTAGE OF STUDENTS BY SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS ACROSS CENTRES	PERCENTAGE
% Low	35,51%
% Medium-Low	36,62%
% Medium High	21,33%
% High	6,54%

Results from this phase indicate high levels of adequacy and relevance in all indicators (only 1 indicator had less than 3 average score out of 4 in the sum of those two dimensions). In addition, 247 qualitative comments were collected from the macro and meso participants in this phase. All indicators in this phase were rated above the average scores in Clarity. In a scale from 1 to 4 the lowest score was 2,58 for meso-level respondents on indicator D4.2 (Legislation and practice conditioning (LPC) the acquisition of superior legal status) and for macro-level respondents, the lowest score was 2,67 on indicator O2.2.2 (Children maintain their cultural identity while adopting key host country cultural values and intercultural competences), O2.2.2 was eliminated in this last validation round. Indicator D4.2 remained although it received a lower score in the dimensions of "Adequacy and relevance" and "clarity" in general, compared with indicator D4.7 (Clear and effective leadership (regional and national) on intercultural values against xenophobia, prejudice and stereotypes) which had been the lowest ranked when considering only the national-level indicators in the dimension of Adequacy by macro actors. In addition, by measuring the easiness to accede to a permanent status in destination country, indicator D4.2 already includes the integration dimensions that indicator D4.7 aims to identify, but it does in a direct way, whereas indicator D4.7 was split by indirect dimensions which, in the case of children, are less relevant than directly taking into account access to nationality.

Regarding the Accessibility dimension which rated from 1 to 2, all scores were also above the average for both macro and meso-level respondents. Nevertheless, the lowest score was 1,59 for meso-level respondents on indicator D3.3.3 (Low expectations / stereotypes among teachers towards certain groups) and 1,64 for macro-level respondents on indicator D3.3.4 (Diversity among teachers and school personnel), both indicators were also eliminated in this phase.

3.3.2 Micro stakeholders: methodology and results

The validation with children was carried out in 17 workshops conducted across the 6 IMMERSE countries during the months of December 2019 and February 2020. A total of 86 migrant children and adolescents participated in these workshops, represented diversified profiles as summarized in the tables below.

Table 16. Percentage of participating children by country

HOST COUNTRY	PERCENTAGE
Belgium	18,60%
Greece	17,44%
Spain	12,79%
Ireland	19,77%
Italy	12,79%
Germany	18,60%

Table 17. Percentage of age ranges

AGE RANGE	PERCENTAGE
6-9	27,91%
10-12	22,09%
13-15	19,77%
16-18	30,23%

A common methodology was applied for all workshops, in which the 15 indicators based on survey items to be collected from children were to be assessed by the children themselves. These indicators and the corresponding survey items were reviewed for their adaptation to smaller children (6 to 9 years old). 6 of them were considered not appropriate for this group, and will not be collected (nor available in the dashboard) for these ages, whereas the wording and formulation of the remaining 9 indicators (and corresponding survey items) were adjusted and supported with visual aids to be assessed by the smaller children in separate workshops.³⁵

In each workshop, the participants were presented with the survey items and were then asked to discuss the clarity, meanings and any issues identified. The children also commented on the perceived relevance of the survey items and indicators, and provided suggestions on ways to improve them, make them clearer and more child-friendly, as well as more interesting and relevant on their views. The findings in each workshops and country were reported in a standard form to be

³⁵ All partners were in charge of translating the original as well as the adapted formulations to the languages spoken in their respective countries.

evaluated in a joint manner, thus ensuring the consideration of different contexts and backgrounds on an equal footing. The assessment of the clarity (and relevance) of most of the survey items and indicators was overwhelmingly good across the board, with participants reporting to understand correctly the items and valuing them as “important”, even wanting to further comment on them and discuss the underlying topics on the spot. However:

- This pattern found a major exception in the difficulties encountered by smaller children (6-9 year-old) in all countries to understand, follow or keep concentrated while answering several of the questions, despite having simplified and adjusted all of the questions presented to this age group. By the age of 6 children most children are just starting their reading learning and their stage of cognitive development requires more concrete and visual representations. To address these challenges a cartoon-based adaptation with simpler wording will be prepared.
- The older children (10-18) also provided further comments and suggestions involving minor modifications to make the survey items more understandable (and interesting) for children of their age, and very interestingly, for the smaller children as well. We immensely valued these suggestions and have incorporated most of them (where there was a generalized consensus or particularly insightful improvements) as they will certainly increase the ecological validity of the dashboard.
- The general positive assessment of the survey items does not mean that there were no criticisms to particular aspects, but these were largely addressed in the suggestions for improvement. Also, not all indicators and survey items were equally valued as clear and relevant, and this was taken into consideration in the final decision-making together with the assessment of the macro and meso stakeholders.

3.3.3 Aggregate results and final selection

First, the 35 indicators assessed by the stakeholders were ordered by its scores of adequacy and relevance, clarity and accessibility, which provided a quantitative measure of the quality of the indicators. As discussed above, these quantitative assessments were very good with high scores for almost all indicators across all 4 CARA criteria and relatively low variability in the ranking. Those with the lowest scores in both the meso and macro sub-samples were considered as candidates to be dropped, but since scores were quite tight the number of candidates to be dropped was quite larger than 5 and with very small differences between remaining indicators and candidates to be dropped. The final decisions were taken on the bases of the qualitative analysis of children’s comments, as well as meso and macro level stakeholders’ comments in the assessment process. These comments were systematised in one excel sheet and three workgroups of IMMERSE researchers were made in order to review the comments of the stakeholders, adapt the wording of the items where necessary, and make more detailed proposals about the indicators to be dropped based on the issues raised. In this regard, some changes were made in the wording of 12 indicators, mostly with the double aim of making them more understandable for the children from 6 to 12 year old and to reduce the cognitive cost of completing the questionnaire so it could be completed without adult support. Additionally, it was decided that a cartoon-based adaptation of the items to be asked to the group of children from 6 to 9 years old would be prepared to provide of visual aid that complete the meaning of the items for them.

After a last round of co-creative consultation among the partners of the consortium a final agreement on the indicators to be dropped was reached:

- The indicator on the acquisition of refugee status for D4.2 (LPC the acquisition of superior and stable legal status) received the second lowest score in the dimensions of "Adequacy and relevance" (3,186) and "clarity" (2,988) from the macro and meso actors. While the other LPC and D4.2 indicators measure objective possibilities to accede to certain rights, this indicator measures one particular outcome instead (the percentage of positive decisions on refugee status according to the Geneva Convention), which maybe influenced by factors other than policy and political leadership, and which does not say much on the rights available to children recognized by this status (or to other children in similar circumstances but with alternative humanitarian statuses).
- The indicator on D4.7 (Clear and effective leadership - regional and national - on intercultural values, against xenophobia, prejudice and stereotypes) was the lowest ranked between all the macro indicators in the dimension of "adequacy" by macro actors (it received a score of 3.06). The remaining indicators on D4.2 (LPC acquisition of superior and stable status), D4.3 (LPC access to education) and D4.8 (LPC access to health care) already capture the type of political leadership that this indicator aimed to measure by calibrating the easiness to accede to a permanent status and citizenship in destination country, as well as access to the most fundamental rights for children's wellbeing and integration: education and healthcare, whereas the indicator on D4.7 is split by indirect dimensions which, in the case of children, are less relevant (including, for instance, access to labour rights).
- The indicator for factor D6.1 (Experience/perception of negative attitudes) that was based on macro and meso-level attitudes about migration, and the indicator on factor D3.3.4 (Diversity among teachers and school personnel) were dropped because they both received the lowest scores in the average of relevance and adequacy when combining both macro and meso results.
- Finally indicator on D3.3.3 (Low expectations / stereotypes among teachers towards certain groups) was decided to be dropped for receiving the lowest score in accesibility receiving concerns from the macro (1,52) and meso (1,67) stakeholders. Additionally this bad quantitative results were backed by qualitative the most negative comments about its clarity about clarity of the indicator by meso and macro stakeholders, and the need of further clarification for micro stakeholders

Following these decisions, the final IMMERSE dashboard of indicators is constituted by 30 indicators that proxy 28 factors ("Interconnectedness with friends and peers" and "LPC the acquisition of superior legal status" will be composite factors with 2 empirical indicators). No further outcome indicator has been dropped, so as before, all the key outcome dimensions and their main subdimensions are represented in the selection, with the exception of O1.1 (Legal status), O2.2.1 (Children's competence in mother tongue) and O3.1.1 (Children's self-esteem). Nonetheless, 4, 5 and 13 key determinants for each of these outcomes, respectively, are included, which should help ensure a correct balance for capturing the latent variable of integration.

Table 18. IMMERSE dashboard of final selection of outcome indicators

OUTCOMES				N of INDICATORS	
DIMENSION	SUBDIMENSION	FACTOR	LEVEL	OUTCOME	DETERMINANT
01. OUTCOMES IN ACCESS TO RIGHTS	01.1 Legal status	01.1.1 Children's legal status		0	4
	01.2 Access to rights	0.1.2.1 Access to compulsory education		1	3
		0.1.2.2 Access to health care		1	3
02. OUTCOMES IN LANGUAGE & CULTURE	02.1 Host language	02.1.1 Children's competence in host language		1	7
	02.2 Interculturalism	02.2.1 Children's competence in mother tongue		0	4
		02.2.2 Children maintain their cultural identity while adopting new cultural values and intercultural competences	A.Identity B.Values C.Competences	1	8
03. OUTCOMES IN WELL-BEING	03.1 Subjective well-being	03.1.1 Children's self-esteem		0	12
		03.1.2 Children's life satisfaction / happiness		1	12
		03.1.3 Children's sense of belonging		1	12
04. OUTCOMES IN CONNECTEDNESS	04.1 Interconnectedness	04.1.1 Friends and peers	A.Support B.Out school C.Bridges	2	6
		04.1.2 Teachers		1	6
		04.1.3 Institutions		1	8
05. OUTCOMES IN EDUCATIONAL ACHIEVEMENTS	05.1 Academic skills	05.1.1 Children's academic skills		1	12
	05.2 Levels and types of education attained	05.2.1 Children complete compulsory education		1	11
		05.2.2 Children's access formal post-compulsory education		1	11
		05.2.3 Types & levels of formal non-compulsory education attended		1	11

Note: cross-out factors are the ones finally discarded

A total of 10 meso-level determinants and 7 macro-level determinants are included in the selection:

- Most of the 7 macro-level determinants belong to the political leadership cluster, proxied by policies conditioning access to basic rights (4), followed by the cluster on learning support (2) and one LRR indicator on intercultural education.
- The 10 meso-level determinants are concentrated on the clusters of school organization (4), negative attitudes at the local level (3) and supplementary services for learning support and extra-curricular activities at the neighbourhood level (2). Singular indicators have been selected for the clusters of school segregation and counselling services.

Table 19. Dashboard of determinant indicators: clusters of barriers and facilitators

BARRIERS & FACILITATORS			ECOLOGICAL LEVEL	
CLUSTER	FACTOR	LEVEL	MESO	MACRO
POLITICAL LEADERSHIP	D4.7 Clear and effective leadership (regional and national) on intercultural values. against xenophobia. prejudice and stereotypes		0	4
	D4.2 LPC acquisition of superior legal status	A. Nationality B. Permanent residence C. Refugee status		
	D4.3 LPC access to education			
	D4.12 LPC / LRR early education			
	LPC / LRR Scholarships and benefits available			
	D4.8 LPC access to health care			
	D4.9 LPC access to other basic rights (e.g. housing, benefits...)	A. Housing B. Social protection		
	D4.10 LRR: providing resources (legal assistance, social workers, etc.)			
D5.1 Available resources (legal assistance, social workers, accompaniment, etc.)				
SCHOOL SEGREGATION	D3.7.1 Concentration levels in disadvantaged schools		1	0
	D3.7.2 By Presence of diversity (migrant background, ethnicity, languages, disabilities and learning difficulties)			
SCHOOL ORGANIZATION & TEACHERS	D3.2.1 Clear leadership and school identity around intercultural values. against xenophobia. prejudice and stereotypes		3	1
	D3.2.2 Incorporation of multiple languages, cultural expressions, cultural dialogue and exchange in school activities (including cantina, holiday and calendar planning, multi-language website and school information...)			
	D3.2.3 School promotion of parental involvement in school activities, extra-curricular activities and parental associations			
	D3.3.1 Training and support resources on intercultural competences			
	D3.4.5 Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally			

	D4.15.5 LRR Intercultural education			
	D3.3.3 Low expectations / stereotypes among teachers towards certain groups			
ALLOCATION OF STUDENTS	D3.8.1 Criteria for incorporation to educational levels upon arrival			
	D4.19.1 LRR Criteria for incorporation to educational levels upon arrival		0	0
LEARNING SUPPORT	D4.16.1 LRR Preparatory classes dedicated/with focus on language acquisition			
	D3.5.2/3 Language/learning support within/outside mainstream classes			
	D4.16.2 LRR Educational support for migrant children, particularly learning and language support			
	D5.5/6 Supplementary community services for language/learning support		2	2
	D4.16.4 LRR Language/learning support at alternative environments			
	D3.5.4 Extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres			
	D4.16.5 LRR Promotion of extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres			
FOREIGN LANGUAGES AT SCHOOL	D4.15.1 Bilingualism (instruction in 2 languages)		0	0
MENTAL HEALTH SERVICES	D3.6.2 Counselling and therapeutic services		1	0
ETHNIC&CULTURAL POINTS OF SUPPORT	D3.1.1 Languages of communication at school			
	D3.3.4 Teachers' diversity			
	D5.2.1 Presence of ethnic/cultural/migrant networks and communities	A.Networks B.Examples	0	0
NEGATIVE ATTITUDES	D6.1 Experience/perception of negative attitudes	A1.Attitudes macro A2. Attitudes meso B.Fear		
	D6.2 Experience of harassment and/or physical violence (incl. bullying) outside family	A.Experience B.Participation	2	0
TOTAL			9	7

Note: cross-out factors are the ones finally eliminated.

Among the selected indicators, 14 will be based on the re-utilization of secondary data sources and 16 will require the collection of survey data by IMMERSE. Of these, 12 indicators require survey data from children and 4 indicators require survey data from teachers and/or principals.³⁶

³⁶ Survey data from parents will complement 1-2 indicators.

Annex 1. Initial 16 outcomes and 66 barriers and facilitators

Table 20. Components of the integration process of migrant-background children (outcomes)

OUTCOMES OF INTEGRATION		
5 DIMENSIONS	8 SUBDIMENSIONS	16 FACTORS
01. Outcomes in access to rights	01.1 Legal status	01.1.1 Children's legal status
	01.2 Access to rights	01.1.2 Access to compulsory education
		01.1.3 Access to health care
02. Outcomes in language & culture	02.1 Host language	02.1.1 Children's competence in host language
	02.2 Interculturalism	02.2.1 Children's competence in mother tongue
		02.2.1 Children maintain their cultural <i>identity</i> while adopting new cultural <i>values</i> and intercultural <i>competences</i>
03. Outcomes in well-being	03.1 Subjective well-being	03.1.1 Children's self-esteem
		03.1.2 Children's life satisfaction / happiness
		03.1.3 Children's sense of belonging
04. Outcomes in connectedness	04. Interconnectedness	04.1.1 Friends and peers (<i>support and bridges</i>)
		04.1.2 Teachers
		04.1.3 Institutions
05. Outcomes in educational achievements	05.1 Academic skills	05.1.1 Children's academic skills
	05.2 Levels and types of education attained	05.2.1 Children complete compulsory education
		05.2.2 Children access formal non-compulsory education
		05.2.3 Types & levels of (formal) non-compulsory education attended

Table 21. Initial 66 barriers and facilitators

BARRIERS AND FACILITATORS	
3 SCHOOL FACTORS	
3.1	Students
D3.1.1	Languages of communication at school
3.2	School direction
D3.2.1	Clear leadership and school identity around intercultural values. against xenophobia. prejudice and stereotypes
D3.2.2	Incorporation of multiple languages, cultural expressions, cultural dialogue and exchange in school activities (including cantina, holiday and calendar planning, multi-language website and school information...)
D3.2.3	Promotion of parental involvement in school activities, extra-curricular activities and parental associations
3.3	Teachers
D3.3.1	Training and support resources on intercultural competences
D3.3.2	Cultural awareness in communication and relations of teachers with pupils and parents
D3.3.3	Low expectations / stereotypes among teachers towards minority/migrant/low socio-economic background children

D3.3.4	Diversity
3.4	Curriculum
D3.4.1	Bilingualism
D3.4.2	Teaching of foreign language
D3.4.3	Foreign languages available
D3.4.4	Culturally-aware curricula. and representativeness of migrants
D3.4.5	Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally
3.5	Language & learning support
D3.5.1	Preparatory classes
D3.5.2	Language support within/outside mainstream classes
D3.5.3	Learning support within/outside mainstream classes
D3.5.4	Extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres
3.6	School-based mental health services
D3.6.1	School-based (preventive) mental health services
D3.6.2	Counselling and therapeutic services
3.7	Disadvantaged schools / school segregation
D3.7.1	By Socio-economic status of students attending
D3.7.2	By Presence of diversity (migrant background. ethnicity. languages; disabilities and learning difficulties)
D3.7.3	Ratio students-teachers / Number of students at class
3.8	Students separation / tracking
D3.8.1	Criteria for incorporation to educational levels upon arrival
D3.8.2	Separation of students by performance level
D3.8.3	Tracking systems - Separation/selection into different tracks
5. NEIGHBOURHOOD FACTORS	
D5.1	Available resources (legal assistance. social workers. accompaniment. etc.)
D5.2	Presence of co-ethnics
D5.2.1	Presence of ethnic/cultural/migrant networks and communities
D5.2.2	Presence of other children of similar ethnic/cultural backgrounds at school
D5.3	Supplementary community services for health care
D5.4	Supplementary community services for assistance and support – supplementing lack of access or fear to access formal services (unauthorized migrants)
D5.5	Supplementary community services for language support
D5.6	Supplementary community services for learning support
D5.7	Supplementary mental health community services
4 MACRO FACTORS	
LPC = legislation and practice conditioning...	
LRR = legislation. recommendations and resources devoted to...	
D4.1	LPC legal status at entry (or birth)
D4.2	LPC acquisition of superior legal status
D4.3	LPC access to compulsory education
D4.4	LPC access to (formal) non-compulsory education
D4.5	LPC recognition of degrees and effective education attained before arrival
D4.6	LPC / LRR Scholarships and benefits available

D4.7	Clear and effective leadership (regional and national) on intercultural values. against xenophobia. prejudice and stereotypes
D4.8	LPC access to health care
D4.9	LPC access to other basic rights (e.g. housing. benefits...)
D4.10	LRR: providing resources (legal assistance. social workers. etc.)
D4.11	LPC family reunification (in case of separated families)
D4.12	LPC / LRR early education
D4.13	LRR to provide support for school organization
D4.14	LRR Teachers' training for intercultural and multilingual schools and classrooms
D4.15	LRR Curriculum
D4.15.1	Bilingualism (instruction in 2 languages)
D4.15.2	Teaching methodology/curriculum of foreign language
D4.15.3	Foreign languages available
D4.15.4	Culturally-aware curricula. and representativeness of migrants
D4.15.5	Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally
D4.16	LRR Language & learning support
D4.16.1	Preparatory classes dedicated/with focus on language acquisition
D4.16.2	Language support within/outside preparatory classes
D4.16.3	Language support at alternative environments
D4.16.4	Learning support within/outside mainstream classes
D4.16.5	Promotion of extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres
D4.17	LRR mental health
D4.17.1	School-based mental health services
D4.17.2	Outside school mental health services
D4.18	LRR Disadvantaged schools / school segregation
D4.18.1	LRR to support disadvantaged schools
D4.18.2	LRR to tackle segregation
D4.19	LRR Students separation / tracking
D4.19.1	LRR Criteria for incorporation to educational levels upon arrival
D4.19.2	LRR Separation of students by performance level
D4.19.3	System-level / use of early tracking (primary school or transition to secondary)
6. SCHOOL-NEIGH-MACRO FACTORS	
D6.1	Experience/perception of negative attitudes
D6.2	Experience of harassment and/or physical violence (incl. bullying) outside family

Annex 2. Ranking of barriers and facilitators for pre-selection

Table 22. Ranking of barriers and facilitators by IMMENSE researchers

#	FACTOR	VOTES	RELEVANCE	
			MESO	MACRO
1	D6.1 Experience/perception of negative attitudes	4	3	2
2	D6.2 Experience of harassment and/or physical violence (incl. bullying) outside family	4	2	2
3	D3.2.1 Clear leadership and school identity around intercultural values. against xenophobia. prejudice and stereotypes	4	4	1
4	D3.5.2 Language support within/outside mainstream classes	4	2	1
5	D3.4.4 Culturally-aware curricula. and representativeness of migrants	3	2	3
6	D3.7.2 By Presence of diversity (migrant background. ethnicity. languages; disabilities and learning difficulties)	3	3	4
7	D3.4.5 Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally	3	0	2
8	D4.7 Clear and effective leadership (regional and national) on intercultural values. against xenophobia. prejudice and stereotypes	3	1	2
9	D3.2.2 Incorporation of multiple languages. cultural expressions. cultural dialogue and exchange in school activities (including cantina. holiday and calendar planning. multi-language website and school information...)	3	1	1
10	D3.3.3 Low expectations / stereotypes among teachers towards minority/migrant/low socio-economic background children	3	1	1
11	D4.16.3 LRR Language support at alternative environments	3	1	1
12	D3.5.4 Extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres	3	1	1
13	D4.18.2 LRR to tackle segregation	3	1	1
14	D3.8.1 Criteria for incorporation to educational levels upon arrival	3	1	0
15	D4.8 LPC access to health care	3	1	0
16	D5.1 Available resources (legal assistance. social workers. accompaniment. etc.)	3	1	0
17	D4.15.5 Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally	3	0	1
18	D3.3.2 Cultural awareness in communication and relations of teachers with pupils and parents	3	0	0
19	D4.15.1 Bilingualism (instruction in 2 languages)	3	0	0
20	D3.5.3 Learning support within/outside mainstream classes	3	0	0
21	D5.2.1 Presence of ethnic/cultural/migrant networks and communities	3	0	0
22	D3.1.1 Languages of communication at school	2	2	1
23	D4.16.1 Preparatory classes dedicated/with focus on language acquisition	2	2	0
24	D3.6.2 Counselling and therapeutic services	2	1	2
25	D3.3.1 Training and support resources on intercultural competences	2	1	1
26	D3.5.1 Preparatory classes	2	1	1
27	D3.2.3 Promotion of parental involvement in school activities. extra-curricular activities and parental associations	2	1	0
28	D4.16.2 LRR Language support within/outside preparatory classes	2	1	0
29	D4.10 LRR: providing resources (legal assistance. social workers. etc.)	2	1	0
30	D3.3.4 Diversity of teachers	2	0	1
31	D4.15.4 Culturally-aware curricula. and representativeness of migrants	2	0	1
32	D4.16.5 Promotion of extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres	2	0	1
33	D4.3 LPC access to compulsory education	2	0	1
34	D4.5 LPC recognition of degrees and effective education attained before arrival	2	0	1
35	D5.6 Supplementary community services for learning support	2	0	0
36	D4.16.4 Learning support within/outside mainstream classes	2	0	0
37	D4.19.1 LRR Criteria for incorporation to educational levels upon arrival	2	0	0

38	D4.1 LPC legal status at entry (or birth)	2	0	0
39	D4.6 LPC / LRR Scholarships and benefits available	2	0	0
40	D4.9 LPC access to other basic rights (e.g. housing. benefits...)	2	0	0
41	D4.12 LPC / LRR early education	2	0	0
42	D5.2.2 Presence of other children of similar ethnic/cultural backgrounds at school	2	0	0
43	D3.7.1 By Socio-economic status of students attending	1	3	3
44	D3.4.3 Foreign languages available	1	1	1
45	D4.17.1 School-based mental health services	1	1	0
46	D4.18.1 LRR to support disadvantaged schools	1	1	0
47	D4.2 LPC acquisition of superior legal status	1	1	0
48	D3.8.3 Tracking systems - Separation/selection into different tracks	1	0	1
49	D4.19.3 System-level / use of early tracking (primary school or transition to secondary)	1	0	1
50	D4.15.2 Teaching methodology/curriculum of foreign language	1	0	0
51	D5.5 Supplementary community services for language support	1	0	0
52	D4.17.2 Outside school mental health services	1	0	0
53	D4.13 LRR to provide support for school organization	1	0	0
54	D3.8.2 Separation of students by performance level	1	0	0
55	D5.4 Supplementary community services for assistance and support – supplementing lack of access or fear to access formal services (unauthorized migrants)	1	0	0
56	D4.11 LPC family reunification (in case of separated families)	1	0	0
57	D4.14 LRR Teachers' training for intercultural and multilingual schools and classrooms	1	0	0
58	D3.4.1 Bilingualism	1	0	0
59	D3.4.2 Teaching of foreign language	0	0	0
60	D4.15.3 Foreign languages available	0	0	0
61	D3.6.1 School-based (preventive) mental health services	0	0	0
62	D5.7 Supplementary mental health community services	0	0	0
63	D3.7.3 Ratio students-teachers / Number of students at class	0	0	0
64	D4.19.2 LRR Separation of students by performance level	0	0	0
65	D4.4 LPC access to (formal) non-compulsory education	0	0	0
66	D5.3 Supplementary community services for health care	0	0	0

Annex 3. Clusters of barriers and facilitators for pre-selection

Table 23. Cluster-based pre-selection of factors

CLUSTER NEGATIVE ATTITUDES	
1	D6.1 Experience/perception of negative attitudes
2	D6.2 Experience of harassment and/or physical violence (incl. bullying) outside family
CLUSTER SCHOOL ORGANIZATION & TEACHERS	
3	D3.2.1 Clear leadership and school identity around intercultural values. against xenophobia. prejudice and stereotypes
4	D3.2.2 Incorporation of multiple languages. cultural expressions. cultural dialogue and exchange in school activities (including cantina. holiday and calendar planning. multi-language website and school information...)
5	D3.2.3 Promotion of parental involvement in school activities. extra-curricular activities and parental associations
6	D3.3.1 Training and support resources on intercultural competences
	D3.4.4 Culturally-aware curricula. and representativeness of migrants
7	D3.4.5 Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally
	D4.14 LRR Teachers' training for intercultural and multilingual schools and classrooms
	D4.15.4 Culturally-aware curricula. and representativeness of migrants
8	D4.15.5 Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally
	D3.3.2 Cultural awareness in communication and relations of teachers with pupils and parents
9	D3.3.3 Low expectations / stereotypes among teachers towards minority/migrant/low socio-economic background children
CLUSTER SCHOOL SEGREGATION	
10	D3.7.1 By Socio-economic status of students attending
11	D3.7.2 By Presence of diversity (migrant background. ethnicity. languages; disabilities and learning difficulties)
	D3.7.3 Ratio students-teachers / Number of students at class
	D4.13 LRR to provide support for school organization
	D4.18.1 LRR to support disadvantaged schools
	D4.18.2 LRR to tackle segregation
CLUSTER LEARNING SUPPORT	
	D3.5.1 Preparatory classes
12	D3.5.2 Language support within/outside mainstream classes
	D3.5.3 Learning support within/outside mainstream classes
	D5.5 Supplementary community services for language support
13	D5.6 Supplementary community services for learning support
14	D3.5.4 Extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres
15	D4.16.1 Preparatory classes dedicated/with focus on language acquisition
16	D4.16.2 Language support within/outside preparatory classes
17	D4.16.3 Language support at alternative environments
18	D4.16.4 Learning support within/outside mainstream classes
19	D4.16.5 Promotion of extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres
CLUSTER ETHNIC/LINGUISTIC/CULTURAL POINTS OF SUPPORT	
20	D3.1.1 Languages of communication at school
21	D5.2.1 Presence of ethnic/cultural/migrant networks and communities
	D5.2.2 Presence of other children of similar ethnic/cultural backgrounds at school
22	D3.3.4 Diversity among teachers and other school personnel??
CLUSTER POLITICAL LEADERSHIP	

23	D4.7	Clear and effective leadership (regional and national) on intercultural values. against xenophobia. prejudice and stereotypes
	D4.1	LPC legal status at entry (or birth)
24	D4.2	LPC acquisition of superior legal status
25	D4.3	LPC access to compulsory education
	D4.4	LPC access to (formal) non-compulsory education
26	D4.8	LPC access to health care
	D5.3	Supplementary community services for health care
27	D4.9	LPC access to other basic rights (e.g. housing. benefits...)
	D5.4	Supplementary community services for assistance and support – supplementing lack of access or fear to access formal services (unauthorized migrants)
28	D4.12	LPC / LRR early education
	D4.11	LPC family reunification (in case of separated families)
	D5.1	Available resources (legal assistance. social workers. accompaniment. etc.)
29	D4.10	LRR: providing resources (legal assistance. social workers. etc.)
CLUSTER MENTAL HEALTH SERVICES		
	D3.6.1	School-based (preventive) mental health services
30	D3.6.2	Counselling and therapeutic services
	D4.17.1	School-based mental health services
	D5.7	Supplementary mental health community services
	D4.17.2	Outside school mental health services
CLUSTER ALLOCATION OF STUDENTS		
31	D3.8.1	Criteria for incorporation to educational levels upon arrival
	D3.8.2	Separation of students by performance level
	D3.8.3	Tracking systems - Separation/selection into different tracks
32	D4.19.1	LRR Criteria for incorporation to educational levels upon arrival
	D4.19.2	LRR Separation of students by performance level
	D4.19.3	System-level / use of early tracking (primary school or transition to secondary)
	D4.5	LPC recognition of degrees and effective education attained before arrival
33	D4.6	LPC / LRR Scholarships and benefits available
CLUSTER FOREIGN LANGUAGES AT SCHOOL		
	D3.4.1	Bilingualism
	D3.4.2	Teaching of foreign language
	D3.4.3	Foreign languages available
34	D4.15.1	Bilingualism (instruction in 2 languages)
	D4.15.2	Teaching methodology/curriculum of foreign language
	D4.15.3	Foreign languages available

Annex 5. Preselected 50 factors (57 indicators) for DELPHI

FACTOR	DESIRED INDICATOR	Reference source/s	Re-use 2ary source
OUTCOMES			
01.1.1 Children's legal status (dynamic perspective: acquisition of superior statuses)	Children who acquired citizenship by end of year as a share (%) of child residents (non-citizens) by start of the year	Eurostat/administrative	YES
01.1.2 Children's access to compulsory education	Foreign children at school as a share of foreign children in compulsory ages (6-16/18)	Education ministries / Eurostat administrative data on population	YES
01.1.3 Children's access to health care	Share of foreign and/or foreign-born population with children under 16 that had unmet needs for medical examination in the last 12 months	EU-SILC	YES
02.1.1 Children's competence in host language	Share of migrant-background children picking option 3 values in the two items Thinking about communication in [host country], please rate your competence at... <i>For each item: Low 1, Middle 2, High 3</i> - Understanding and speaking [host country instruction language] - Reading and writing [host country instruction language]	Adapted from Sociocultural Adaptation Scale (SCAR)	NO
02.2.1 Children's competence in mother tongue	Share of migrant-background children picking option 3 values in the two items Thinking about communication in [mother tongue], please rate your competence at... <i>For each item: Low 1, Middle 2, High 3</i> - Understanding and speaking [mother tongue] - Reading and writing [mother tongue]	Adapted from Sociocultural Adaptation Scale (SCAR)	NO
02.2.1 Children maintain their cultural identity while adopting key host country cultural values and intercultural competences	A. Share of migrant background children picking the following combinations in the survey item below a. Some of 1-3; and also some of 4-5 b. Some of 1-3; and not 4-5 c. Options 4-5; and not 1-3 d. Only options 6-7; none from 1-5	Based on Eurobarometer	NO
	How close do you feel to the following groups? Please select the 3 you feel the closest to. 1. [Host country] people 2. [City] people 3. Neighbourhood you live in 4. [Origin country] people 5. People with the same religion as you 6. People of your same age 7. People of your same gender B. Average score in the items below among all children How well does each of the following	Based on PISA 2018 Global competences	NO

	<p>statements below describe you? For each item: <i>Very much like me 4 Mostly like me 3 Not much like me 2 Not at all like me 1</i></p> <p>I am interested in how people from various cultures see the world I want to learn how people live in different countries. I respect the values of people from different cultures</p>		
	<p>C. Average score in the items below among all children</p> <p>How well does each of the following statements below describe you? For each item: <i>Not at all like me 1 Not much like me 2 Mostly like me 3 Very much like me 4</i></p> <p>I can adapt easily to a new culture I am capable of overcoming my difficulties in interacting with people from other cultures.</p>	Based on PISA 2018 Global competences	NO
03.1.1 Children's self-esteem	<p>Average score of migrant-background children in item below:</p> <p>I have high self-esteem / I like the way I am Not very true of me 1 - Very true of me 7</p>	Based on Single-item self-esteem scale (Robins et al 2001)	NO
03.1.2 Children's life satisfaction / happiness	<p>Share of migrant-background children that pick options 1-2 in survey item below:</p> <p>Taking all things together, would you say you are: 1 Very happy 2 Quite happy 3 Not very happy 4 Not at all happy</p>	EVS	NO
03.1.3 Children's sense of belonging	<p>Average score in the items below among migrant-background children</p> <p>How frequently do the following occur to you? For each item: <i>1 Almost never, 2 Sometimes, 3 Often, 4 Almost always</i></p> <p>I feel like I belong at my school I can really be myself at school I feel like people at my school care about me</p>	Student subjective wellbeing questionnaire (School connectedness subscale)	NO
04.1.1 Interconnectedness / friends and peers	<p>A. Average score in the items below among migrant-background children</p> <p>How do you feel about the following statements? For each item: <i>Strongly disagree 1, Disagree 2, Agree 3, Strongly agree 4</i></p> <p>My friends really try to help me I have friends with whom I can share joys and sorrows</p>	HBSC survey	NO
	<p>B. Share of migrant-background children selecting option 1 below</p> <p>How much time out school do you spend</p>	ICCS survey	NO

	<p>with friends on a normal day? (choose one)</p> <p>1 No time 2 Less than 30 minutes 3 About 30–60 minutes 4 About 1–2 hours 5 More than 2 hours</p>		
	<p>C. Share of all children selecting option 1 below</p> <p>What proportion of your friends are from a different country of origin than yours, or from a different culture or religion?</p> <p>1 All the same as me 2 More than a half 3 About a half 4 Less than a half 5 Don't have any friends</p>	Community Life Survey UK	NO
04.1.2 Interconnectedness / teachers	<p>Average score in the items below among migrant-background children</p> <p>How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about you and your school?</p> <p><i>For each item: Strongly disagree 1, Disagree 2, Agree 3, Strongly agree 4</i></p> <p>- Most of my teachers really listen to what I have to say - If I need extra help, I will receive it from my teachers</p>	ICCS survey	NO
04.1.3 Interconnectedness / institutions	<p>Average score in the items below among migrant-background children</p> <p>How much trust you have in the following institutions in [host country]</p> <p><i>For each item: from 0 to 10</i></p> <p>Schools and teachers Doctors and hospitals Police & justice system NGOs and associations Church, mosque or other religious institutions Public services (library, swimming pools, social workers...)</p>	Based on Eurobarometer	NO
05.1.1 Children's academic skills	<p>Share of low achievers in reading, mathematics and science among foreign, foreign-born and 2nd generation 15-year-olds</p>	PISA	YES
05.2.1 Children complete compulsory education	<p>Share of persons with compulsory education completed among foreign-born population aged 16-20 who arrived in the host country before age 15</p>	PIAAC	YES
05.2.2 Children remain in formal education beyond compulsory levels (i.e. access to formal post-compulsory education)	<p>Share of persons who were not involved in any education or training during the four weeks preceding the survey among foreign-born young adult people (18-24) with lower secondary education or less (Early leavers)</p>	Eurostat / LFS	YES
05.2.3 Types and levels of (formal) non-compulsory education attended	<p>Share of persons who have completed or are currently attending upper secondary or tertiary studies in the host country, among foreign-born population aged 16-</p>	PIAAC	YES

	24 and with studies completed or currently studying in host country		
DETERMINANTS			
POLITICAL LEADERSHIP			
D4.7 Clear and effective leadership (regional and national) on intercultural values. against xenophobia, prejudice and stereotypes	<p>MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the policy strand Anti-discrimination averaging the following policy dimensions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definitions and concepts: Are all residents protected from racial, ethnic, religious, and nationality discrimination? (0-100) - Fields of application: Is racial, ethnic, religious, and nationality discrimination outlawed in all areas of life? (0-100) - Enforcement mechanisms: Are victims of discrimination encouraged to bring forward a case? (0-100) - Equality policies: Can all residents benefit from strong government commitments to equality and independent equality policies? (0-100) 	MIPEX policy indicators	YES
D4.2 Legislation and practice conditioning (LPC)... acquisition of superior legal status	<p>Average score of MIPEX policy dimensions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to nationality / Eligibility: How long must migrants wait to naturalise? Are their children and grandchildren born in the country entitled to become citizens? (0-100) - Access to nationality / Conditions for acquisition: Are applicants encouraged to succeed through basic conditions for naturalisation? (0-100) 	MIPEX policy indicators	YES
D4.3 LPC access to compulsory education	<p>Average score of MIPEX policy indicators 45, 44 and 124 (0-100)</p> <p>45. Compulsory education as legal right (Access is a legal right for all compulsory-age children in the country, regardless of their residence status (includes undocumented))</p> <p>Scores: <i>100 - Explicit obligation in law for all categories of migrants to have same access as nationals</i> <i>50 - Implicit obligation for all children (No impediment to equal access in law. e.g. No link between compulsory education and residence, or no category of migrant excluded. Please specify)</i> <i>0 - Restrictions in law on access for some categories of migrants (please specify)</i></p> <p>44. Support to access pre-primary and compulsory education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. State-supported targeted measures (e.g. financial support, campaigns and other means) to increase participation of migrant pupils b. Targeted measures to increase migrant 	MIPEX policy indicators	YES

	<p>pupils' successful completion of compulsory education (e.g. early school leaving/second chance programs); Note: Use definition of pre-primary/compulsory in your country (please specify)</p> <p>Scores: <i>100 - Both of these (please specify content of a and b)</i> <i>50 - One (specify)</i> <i>0 - None. Migrants only benefit from general support for all students (and targeted non-governmental initiatives where provided)</i></p> <p>124. [Anti-discrimination] Law covers education (primary and secondary level): a) race and ethnicity b) religion and belief c) nationality <i>100 - All three grounds</i> <i>50 - Two grounds</i> <i>0 - Ground a, none, or only based on international standards or constitution, subject to judicial interpretation</i></p>		
D4.12 Legislation, Recommendations and Resources devoted to (LRR)... early education	Foreign children at pre-primary school as a share of foreign children in pre-primary age range (start age of pre-primary and up to start age of primary studies)	Education ministries / Eurostat administrative data on population	YES
D4.8 LPC access to health care	<p>MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the policy strand Health, averaging the following policy dimensions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Entitlement to health services: Are health entitlements equal for immigrants and for nationals? (0-100) - Policies to facilitate access: Do policies assist immigrants in accessing their health entitlements? (0-100) - Responsive health services: Are health services adapting to become more responsive to immigrants' needs? (0-100) - Measures to achieve change: Does government support health services to become more responsive to immigrants' needs? (0-100) 	MIPEX policy indicators	YES
D4.9 LPC access to other basic rights, such as housing and welfare	A. Foreign-born persons living with dependent children in substandard accommodation as a share of foreign-born persons living with dependent children	EU-SILC	YES
	<p>B. Average score of MIPEX policy indicators 125 and 126 (0-100)</p> <p>125. Social protection. Law covers social protection, including social security: a) race and ethnicity b) religion and belief c) nationality <i>100 - All three grounds</i> <i>50 - Two grounds</i> <i>0 - Ground a, none, or only based on international standards or constitution, subject to judicial interpretation</i></p>	MIPEX policy indicators	YES

	<p>126. Access to and supply of public goods and services, including housing. Law covers access to and/or supply of goods and services available to the public, including housing:</p> <p>a) race and ethnicity b) religion and belief c) nationality</p> <p>100 - All three grounds 50 - Two grounds 0 - Ground a, none, or only based on international standards or constitution, subject to judicial interpretation</p>		
<p>D4.10 LRR providing resources relevant for refugees and migrants (e.g. legal assistance. social workers. etc.)</p>	<p>Percentage of payments (as reported by member state to the Commission) during the 2014-2017 period, as a share of the 2014-2020 AMIF commitments made to that member state</p> <p>Note: The AMIF is intended “to promote the efficient management of migration flows and the implementation, strengthening and development of a common Union approach to asylum and immigration” and at least 20% of the funds should be allocated to integration and at least another 20% to asylum. Specific AMIF funding amounts are allocated to each state member basic allocation keys , payments for programme activities are made on the basis of eligible expenditure.</p>	<p>EC Communication (as of 31 December 2017)</p>	<p>YES</p>

SCHOOL SEGREGATION

<p>D3.7.1 Disadvantaged schools by Socio-economic status of students attending</p>	<p>Share of schools with the following percentages of students from socioeconomically disadvantaged homes: 10-30%, 30-50%, 50-70%, more than 70%</p> <p>What is the percentage in this school of: - Students from socioeconomically disadvantaged homes</p>	<p>PISA</p>	<p>YES</p>
<p>D3.7.2 Disadvantaged schools by Presence of diversity (migrant background. ethnicity. languages; disabilities and learning difficulties)</p>	<p>Share of schools with the following percentages of students with different heritage language to language of instruction: 10-30%, 30-50%, 50-70%, more than 70%</p> <p>What is the percentage in this school of: - Students whose <heritage language> is different from <test language> _____ - Students with special needs _____</p>	<p>PISA</p>	<p>YES</p>

SCHOOL ORGANIZATION & TEACHERS

<p>D3.2.1 Clear leadership and school identity around intercultural values. against xenophobia. prejudice and stereotypes</p>	<p>Share of schools responding Yes to the following survey item</p> <p>In your school, are you implementing policies and practices to teach students how to deal with ethnic and cultural discrimination? (choose one)</p>	<p>TALIS</p>	<p>YES</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes, there are official documented policies and practices that we are implementing - Yes, although there are not policies and practices - No, there are official documented policies and practices but we are not implementing them yet - No, there are no such provisions 		
D3.2.2 Incorporation of multiple languages, cultural expressions, cultural dialogue and exchange in school activities (including cantina, holiday and calendar planning, multi-language website and school information...)	<p>Score in MIPEX policy indicator 63 (0-100):</p> <p>Adapting daily school life to reflect diversity: Daily life at school can be adapted based on cultural or religious needs in order to avoid exclusion of pupils. Such adaptations might include one or a few of the following: Changes to the existing school timetable and religious holidays; educational activities; dress codes and clothing; school menus.</p> <p>Scores</p> <p>100 - State regulations or guidelines concerning local adaptation (please specify which adaptations).</p> <p>50 - Law allows for local or school-level discretion (please specify which adaptations).</p> <p>0 - No specific adaptation foreseen in law.</p>	MIPEX policy indicators	YES
D3.2.3 School promotion of parental involvement in school activities. extra-curricular activities and parental associations	<p>Share of schools answering Yes to any of the items below</p> <p>Do the following statements about parental involvement apply to your school?</p> <p>For each item: Y/N</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Our school designs effective forms of school-to-home and home-to-school communications about school programmes and children's progress. - Our school provides information and ideas for families about how to help students at home with homework and other curriculum-related activities, decisions, and planning. 	PISA	YES
D3.3.1 Training and support resources on intercultural competences	<p>Score in MIPEX policy indicator 64: Teacher+School principals training to reflect diversity (training and professional development programmes require intercultural education and the appreciation of cultural diversity for all teachers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Topic required in pre-service training in order to qualify as a teacher; b. Topic required in obligatory in-service professional development training) <p>Scores:</p> <p>100 - A or B required</p> <p>50 - A or B offered extensively to teachers</p> <p>0 - A or B only on ad hoc / project basis</p>	MIPEX policy indicators	YES
D3.4.5 Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally	Share of schools answering positively to survey item below	Based on PISA	NO

	<p>Does the school teach students about different cultural perspectives and intercultural competences (such as how to solve conflicts with people from different backgrounds in the classroom)?</p> <p>Yes, it is part of the curriculum</p> <p>Yes, we have a policy to introduce this type of contents in the classes and activities</p> <p>Yes, teachers can incorporate these contents in their classes</p> <p>No</p>		
D4.15.5 LRR Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally	<p>Average score in MIPEX policy indicators 60 and 62</p> <p>60. School curriculum to reflect diversity: The official aims of intercultural education include the appreciation of cultural diversity, and is delivered:</p> <p>a. As a stand-alone curriculum subject;</p> <p>b. Integrated throughout the curriculum.</p> <p>Scores:</p> <p>100 - Both</p> <p>50 - One (specify)</p> <p>0 - Intercultural education not included in curriculum, or intercultural education does not include appreciation of cultural diversity (please specify).</p> <p>62. Adapting curriculum to reflect diversity (The school curricula and teaching materials can be modified to reflect changes in the diversity of the school population:</p> <p>a. State guidance on curricular change to reflect both national and local population variations;</p> <p>b. Inspection, evaluation and monitoring of implementation of (a)</p> <p>Scores:</p> <p>100 - Both of these.</p> <p>50 - One of these.</p> <p>0 - None.</p>	MIPEX policy indicators	YES
D3.3.3 Low expectations / stereotypes among teachers towards minority/migrant/low socio-economic background children	<p>Average score per school across respondents (for the 2 items below):</p> <p>Thinking about teachers in your school: to how many of them do the following statements apply?</p> <p>For each item: None or almost none of them 1, Some of them 2, Most of them 3, All or almost all of them 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - They have lower academic expectations for students of some cultural groups - They say negative things about people of some cultural groups 	PISA	NO

ALLOCATION OF STUDENTS

D3.8.1 Criteria for incorporation to educational levels upon arrival	Adequacy rate: % of migrant-background students enrolled in the educational level that theoretically corresponds to their age	PLUTARCO	YES
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<p>D4.19.1 LRR Criteria for incorporation to educational levels upon arrival</p>	<p>Score in MIPEX policy indicator 46: How is prior learning and language competency of migrant students assessed: a. Assessment with standardised quality criteria and tools; b. Requirement to use trained staff with specialised qualifications c. Other (please specify) Scores: 100 - Both of these 50 - One of these 0 - Case-by-case assessment by school staff without standardised criteria or training</p>	<p>MIPEX</p>	<p>YES</p>
<p>D4.6 LPC / LRR Scholarships and benefits available</p>	<p>Score in MIPEX policy indicator 8: Equality of access to study grants: What categories of TCNs have equal access? a. Long-term residents b. Residents on temporary work permits (excluding seasonal) c. Residents on family reunion permits (same as sponsor) Score: 100 - All of them 50 - A and (C or certain categories of B) 0 - Only A or None</p>	<p>MIPEX</p>	<p>YES</p>

LEARNING SUPPORT

<p>D4.16.1 LRR Preparatory classes dedicated/with focus on language acquisition</p>	<p>Whether there are (state/regional-level) provisions of preparatory classes for newly arrived students with focus on language/curriculum acquisition</p>	<p>PISA</p>	<p>NO</p>
<p>D3.5.2 Learning and language support within/outside mainstream classes</p>	<p>Share of schools with at least 2 teachers/assistants full time (part-time to be counted as 0.5) in any of the capacities listed in the survey item below: Approximately how many staff does your school currently have in the following capacities? <i>Please indicate the number employed on a full-time and part-time basis.</i> - Learning support/resource teachers - Language support teachers - Special needs assistants - Other teaching assistants (staff help with homework-room where students can do their homework)</p>	<p>TALIS</p>	<p>NO</p>
<p>D4.16.2 LRR Language and learning support within/outside mainstream classes</p>	<p>Score in MIPEX policy indicator 51: Provision of support to learn language of instruction (average a-c) a. Language instruction. Provision of continuous and ongoing education support in language(s) of instruction for migrant pupils: a) In compulsory education (both primary and secondary); b) In pre-primary education. Note: Migrant pupils may be placed in the mainstream classroom or a separate</p>	<p>MIPEX</p>	<p>YES</p>

	<p>classroom for a transitional phase. This question relates to language support in either case. <i>Scores: 100 - Both / 50 - One (specify) / 0 - No provision. Only through private or community initiatives</i></p> <p>b. Communicative/academic fluency. Provision includes: a) Communicative literacy (general fluency in reading, writing, and communicating in the language); b) Academic literacy (fluency in studying, researching, and communicating in the language in the school academic setting) <i>Scores: 100 - Both / 50 - One (specify) / 0 - Level/goals not specified or defined</i></p> <p>c. Language instruction standards. Provision includes quality measures: a) Requirement for courses to use established second-language learning standards; b) Requirement for teachers to be specialised and certified in these standards; c) Curriculum standards are monitored by a state body <i>Scores: 100 - Two or more of these (please specify content of a and b) / 50 - At least one (specify) / 0 - None of these</i></p>		
D5.6 Supplementary community services for learning/ language support	<p>Share of positive answers to survey item below</p> <p>Are there services in the community providing learning support for students (to help them with homework, language learning, etc.) and that you can access ? Yes, and I do use them Yes, but I do not use any No, there is nothing I can afford No, there is nothing I am aware of I don't know</p>	Self-elaboration	NO
D4.16.3 LRR Language/learning support at alternative environments	<p>Score in MIPEX policy indicator 53:</p> <p>Targeted policies to address educational situation of migrant groups: a) Systematic provision of guidance (e.g. teaching assistance, homework support); b) Systematic provision of financial resources <i>Scores: 100 - Both of these (please specify content of a and b) 50 - One (specify) 0 - None. Migrants only benefit from general support. If there is targeted support for migrants, it is only through voluntary initiatives.</i></p>	MIPEX	YES
D3.5.4 Extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres	<p>Share of migrant-background children providing positive answers to at least one of the survey items below</p>	Self-elaboration	NO

	<p>Are there extra-curricular activities (such as sports, arts, music, additional languages, etc.) in your school that you can access ?</p> <p>Yes, and I do use them Yes, but I do not use any No, there is nothing I can afford No, there is nothing I am aware of I don't know</p> <p>Are there extra-curricular activities (such as sports, arts, music, additional languages, etc.) in your community that you can access ?</p> <p>Yes, and I do use them Yes, but I do not use any No, there is nothing I can afford No, there is nothing I am aware of I don't know</p>		
D4.16.5 LRR Promotion of extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres	Whether there are (state/regional-level) regulations/recommendations for Extra-curricular activities to support the integration of migrant students (at primary, general secondary general education and IVET)	EURYDICE	YES

FOREIGN LANGUAGES AT SCHOOL

D4.15.1 Bilingualism (instruction in 2 languages)	Whether there are (state/regional-level) provisions for Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), i.e. bilingual program involving either a foreign language, a regional/minority language or a 2nd national-level official language from pre-primary to upper secondary (ISCED levels 0 to 3)	EURYDICE	YES
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MENTAL HEALTH SERVICES

D3.6.2 Counselling and therapeutic services at school	<p>Share of schools providing a positive answer in survey item below:</p> <p>Does your school provide counselling and therapeutic services?</p> <p>1 Yes 2 No, but we derive to / work with specialized services 3 No, we only do this informally 4 No, we don't provide this type of services</p>	Self-elaboration	NO
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ETHNIC/LINGUISTIC/CULTURAL POINTS OF SUPPORT

D3.1.1 Languages of communication at school	<p>Average number of languages declared per school</p> <p>What language or language(s) do your teachers or peers use in your school aside from the language(s) of instruction?</p> <p><Language 1> <Language 2> <Language 3></p>	Based on PISA Global Competences	NO
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	< ...etc. > Other languages (specify)		
D5.2.1 Presence of ethnic/cultural/migrant networks and communities	A. Share of migrant-background population at municipal (<300.000) or district level (>300.000)	Population registers	YES
	B. Share of all children answering positively to survey item below: Do you know some person(s) of migrant origin in your community that are an inspiring example for you? Yes, plenty of them Yes, several Yes, at least one No Don't know	Self-elaboration	NO
D3.3.4 Diversity among teachers and school personnel	Share of schools that respond positively to survey item below: Does this school employ teachers of more than one cultural or ethnic background? Y/N If yes: Could you tell me approximately in which proportion? Less than 10% from 10 to 25% From 25% to 50% Over 50%	Based on PISA Global Competences	NO

NEGATIVE ATTITUDES

D6.1 Experience/perception of negative attitudes	Average score in survey item below: Is [country] made a worse or a better place to live by people coming to live here from other countries? <i>Choose on from worse place to live 0 to better place to live 10</i>	ESS	YES
	Share of migrant-background children who answer positively to survey item below: Do you avoid certain places (such as shops, cafes, public transportation or some particular neighbourhood) for fear of being treated badly because of your cultural or ethnic background? Y/N	Based on EU-MIDIS	NO
D6.2 Experience of harassment and/or physical violence (incl. bullying) outside family	A. Share of migrant-background children responding 2-5 in the survey item below Have you been bullied at school or by schoolmates (in the neighbourhood or in the cyberspace) in the past couple of months? 1 I have not been bullied 2 It has only happened once or twice 3 It has happened 2 or 3 times a month 4 About once a week 5 Several times a week	Based on HBSC	NO
	B. Share of all children responding 2-5 in the survey item below Have you taken part in bullying some	Based on HBSC	NO

	<p>schoolmate (at school, in the neighbourhood or in the cyberspace) in the past couple of months?</p> <p>1 I have not bullied anyone 2 It has only happened once or twice 3 It has happened 2 or 3 times a month 4 About once a week 5 Several times a week</p>		
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Annex 6. Content-validated factors (31) and indicators (35) for ecological validation

FINAL FACTOR	FINAL INDICATOR	Reference source	Re-utilize 2ARY source
01.2.1 Children's access to compulsory education	<p>Scholarization rates. Proxied by: foreign children enrolled at school as a share of foreign children in compulsory ages <i>Note: we use citizenship (foreign children) as a proxy of migrant-background (country of birth and parents' country of birth) because data on school enrollment is more often available by citizenship than by migration-background (country of birth and parents' country of birth)</i></p> <p>Data source: administrative data and Eurostat</p>	original	YES
01.2.3 Children's access to health care	<p>Difference in share of migrant-background and native respondents with children under 16 that had unmet needs for medical examination in the last 12 months</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM Was there any time during the past 12 months when [any of] your child[ren] (aged 0-15) really needed medical examination or treatment (excluding dental examination or treatment)? Y/N [If yes] Did your child[ren] have a medical examination or treatment each time it was really needed? Y/N [If yes] What was the main reason for not having a medical examination or treatment? 1. Could not afford to (too expensive) 2. Waiting list or the time needed to obtain an appointment was too long 3. Could not take the time because of work, care of other children or of other persons 4. Too far to travel or no means of transportation 5. Other reason</p> <p>Data source: EU-SILC survey (ad hoc module every 5 years, last in 2017). Survey data might be collected from children (IMMERSE).</p>	EU-SILC survey	YES
02.1.1 Children's competence in host language	<p>Average score of migrant/background students in the survey items below</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM</p> <p>Imagine the following situations: A. You need to request some information from the school in <main language>. Do you feel confident about explaining yourself and understanding the information provided to you? 1 I don't feel confident at all 2 I feel a little confident 3 I feel very confident</p> <p>B. A new teacher gives you instructions for an assignment in <main language>. Do you feel confident about understanding the instructions and explaining any doubts you may have? 1 I don't feel confident at all 2 I feel a little confident 3 I feel very confident</p>	original	

	<p>Data source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE). This question will be adapted to children aged 6-10</p>		
<p>02.2.2 Children maintain their cultural identity while adopting key host country cultural values and intercultural competences</p>	<p>Share of migrant background children picking the following combinations in the survey item below</p> <p>a. Some of 1-3; and also some of 4-6 b. Some of 1-3; and not 4-6 c. Some of 4-6; and not 1-3 d. Only options 7-9; none from 1-6</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM</p> <p>Do you feel close to the following groups? For each group: Y/N [For those Y, if more than 3] To which ones do you feel the closest? (maximum 3)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. [Host country] people 2. [City] people 3. People from neighbourhood you live in 4. [Origin country] people 5. People with the same mother tongue as you 6. People with the same religion as you 7. People of your same age 8. People of your same gender 9. People with your same interests and hobbies <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE). This question will not be asked to children aged 6-10</p>	<p>original</p>	
<p>03.1.2 Children's life satisfaction / happiness</p>	<p>Difference in share of migrant-background children and native children that pick options 1-2 in survey item below</p> <p><i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage)</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM</p> <p>Taking all things together, would you say you are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Very happy 2 Quite happy 3 Not very happy 4 Not at all happy <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE)</p>	<p>EVS</p>	
<p>03.1.3 Children's sense of belonging</p>	<p>Average score in the survey items below among migrant-background children</p> <p><i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage)</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM</p> <p>How frequently do the following occur to you? For each item: 1 Almost never, 2 Sometimes, 3 Often, 4 Almost always</p> <p>I feel like I belong at my school I can really be myself at school I feel like people at my school care about me</p> <p><i>Note: the selected indicator focuses on school belonging acknowledging the centrality of schools for the integration of migrant-children in general, and for their sense of belonging in the host country in particular</i></p>	<p>Student subjective wellbeing questionnaire (School connectedness subscale)</p>	

	<p>Data source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE)</p>		
<p>04.1.1 Interconnectedness / Friends and peers</p>	<p>A. Difference in the average score of migrant-background children and native children in the items below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM How do you feel about the following statements? For each item: Strongly disagree 1, Disagree 2, Agree 3, Strongly agree 4 - My friends really try to help me - I have friends with whom I can share joys and sorrows - My friends stand up for me if someone mistreats me</p> <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE)</p> <p>B. Share of all children (migrant-background and native) selecting option #1 in both survey items below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM How many of your friends were born in a different country than yours? 1 All the same as me 2 More than a half 3 About a half 4 Less than a half 5 Don't have any friends</p> <p>How many of your friends are from a different religion or culture? 1 All the same as me 2 More than a half 3 About a half 4 Less than a half 5 Don't have any friends</p> <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE). This question will not be asked to children 6-10</p>	<p>Original inspired by HBSC</p> <p>Original adapted by Community Life Survey UK</p>	
<p>04.1.2 Interconnectedness / Teachers</p>	<p>Difference in average score between migrant-background and native children in the survey items below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about you and your school? For each item: Strongly disagree 1, Disagree 2, Agree 3, Strongly agree 4</p>	<p>ICCS survey</p>	

	<p>- My teachers really try to help me - Most of my teachers really listen to what I have to say - My teachers will stand up for me if someone mistreats me</p> <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE).</p>		
04.1.3 Interconnectedness / Institutions	<p>Difference in average score between migrant-background and native children in the survey items below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM How much trust you have in the following institutions in [host country] For each item: from 0 to 10 a. Teachers and schools b. Doctors and hospitals c. Police & justice system</p> <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE). This question will be adapted for children 6-10</p>	original	
05.1.1 Children's academic skills	<p>Difference in the share of low achievers in reading, mathematics and science among migrant-background and native children (15-year-olds) <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>Data source: PISA</p>	PISA survey	YES
05.2.1 Children complete compulsory education	<p>Share of persons with compulsory education completed among foreign-born population aged 16-20 who arrived in the host country before age 15 <i>Note: the limit of 16 refers to the start of non-compulsory age, and shall be adapted accordingly in countries with a different limit</i></p> <p>Data source: PIAAC</p>	PIAAC survey	YES
05.2.2 Children remain in formal education beyond compulsory levels	<p>Difference in share of early leavers among foreign-born and non-foreign born persons aged 18-24 <i>Note: "Early leaver from education and training" refers to a person aged 18 to 24 who has completed at most lower secondary education (<INSERT HERE THE CORRESPONDING LABEL IN YOUR NATIONAL EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM >) and is not involved in further education or training (formal or informal)</i></p> <p>Data source: Eurostat/EU-LFS</p>	Eurostat/EU-LFS	YES
05.2.3 Types and levels of (formal) non-compulsory education attended	<p>Difference in share of foreign-born and non-foreign born population aged 16-24 who have completed (or are currently studying) upper secondary or tertiary studies in the survey country <i>Note: the limit of 16 refers to the start of non-compulsory age, and shall be adapted accordingly in countries with a different limit</i></p> <p>Data source: PIAAC (2011/2, next in 2021/2; unavailable in Greece and French community in Belgium)</p>	PIAAC survey	YES

<p>D4.7 Clear and effective leadership (regional and national) on intercultural values (against xenophobia, prejudice and stereotypes)</p>	<p>MIPEX overall policy score (0-100) <i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>The MIPEX overall policy score averages the 8 policy areas (see below), providing the most robust measure of the policy contexts promoting equal treatment and equal opportunities. The 8 policy areas include dimensions and indicators that are not directly relevant for children (e.g. labour market policy) but still have an overall impact on the children's families and, most importantly, contribute to the overall policy climate and policy narrative regarding immigration, integration and inclusion. This per se is another determinant for the integration outcomes of children. The policy dimensions of MIPEX are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. LABOUR MARKET MOBILITY. Do legally-resident foreign citizens have comparable workers' rights and opportunities like nationals to access jobs and improve their skills? 2. FAMILY REUNION FOR FOREIGN CITIZENS. Do legally resident foreign citizens have a facilitated right to reunite in their families? 3. EDUCATION. Are all the children of immigrants encouraged to achieve and develop in school like the children of nationals? 4. POLITICAL PARTICIPATION. Do legally resident foreign citizens have comparable opportunities as nationals to participate in political life? 5. PERMANENT RESIDENCE. Do temporary legal residents have facilitated access to a long-term residence permit? 6. ACCESS TO NATIONALITY. Are legal immigrants encouraged to naturalise and are their children born in the country entitled to become full citizens? 7. ANTI-DISCRIMINATION. Do all residents have effective legal protection from racial, ethnic, religious, and nationality discrimination in all areas of life? 8. HEALTH. Is the health system responsive to immigrants' needs? <p>Source: http://www.mipex.eu</p>	<p>MIPEX policy indicators</p>	<p>YES</p>
<p>D4.2 Legislation and practice conditioning (LPC) the acquisition of superior legal status</p>	<p>A. MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the policy strand Access to Nationality <i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>MIPEX Access to Nationality Strand aims to measure whether legal immigrants are encouraged to naturalise and whether their children born in the country are entitled to become full citizens. Its score averages the scores in the following policy dimensions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> D1. Eligibility (How long must migrants wait to naturalise? Are their children and grandchildren born in the country entitled to become citizens?) * D2. Conditions for acquisition (Are applicants encouraged to succeed through basic conditions for naturalisation?)* D3. Security status (Does the state protect applicants from discretionary procedures?) * 	<p>MIPEX policy indicators</p>	<p>YES</p>

	<p>D4. Dual nationality (Can naturalising migrants and their children be citizens of more than one country?) *</p> <p>Source: http://www.mipex.eu/access-nationality</p> <p>* D1 averages the following indicators: 98. Residence period 99. Permits considered 100. Periods of prior-absence allowed 101. Requirements for spouses and partners (a. Spouses of nationals, b. partners of nationals, c. special exemptions) 102. Birth-right citizenship for second generation 103. Birth-right citizenship for third generation</p> <p>* D2 averages the following indicators: 104. Naturalisation language requirement (a. level, b. exemption, c. cost, d. support, e. courses) 105. Naturalisation integration requirement (a. form, b. exemption, c. cost, d. support, e. courses) 106. Economic resources 107. Criminal record 108. Good character 109. Cost of application</p> <p>* D3 averages the following indicators: 110. Maximum duration of procedure 111. Additional grounds for refusal 112. Discretionary powers in refusal 113. Legal protection 114. Protection against withdrawal of citizenship (a. grounds, time limits, statelessness protections)</p> <p>* D4 averages the following indicators: 115. Dual nationality for first generation (a. Renunciation requirement; b. Renunciation exemptions) 116. Dual nationality for second/third generation (at birth or before majority, facilitated, not facilitated)</p>		
	<p>B. MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the policy strand Access to Permanent Residence</p> <p><i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>MIPEX Access to Permanent Residence aims to measure whether temporary legal residents have facilitated access to a long-term residence permit. Its score averages the scores in the following policy dimensions: D1. Eligibility (Can all temporary legal residents apply for a long-term residence permit?)* D2. Conditions for acquisition (Do applicants for long-term residence have to fulfil the same basic conditions in society?)* D3. Security status (Does the state protect applicants from discretionary procedures?)* D4. Rights associated with status (Do long-term residents have the same residence and socio-economic rights?)*</p> <p>Source http://www.mipex.eu/permanent-residence</p> <p>* D1 averages the following indicators: 80. Residence period 81. Permits considered 82. Time counted as pupil/student</p>	<p>MIPEX policy indicators</p>	<p>YES</p>

	<p>83. Periods of prior-absence allowed</p> <p>* D2 averages the following indicators: 84. Language requirement 85. Economic resources 86. Cost of application</p> <p>* D3 averages the following indicators: 87. Maximum duration of procedure 88. Duration of validity of permit 89. Renewable permit 90. Periods of absence allowed 91. Grounds for rejection, withdrawal, refusal 92. Personal circumstances considered before expulsion 93. Expulsion precluded 94. Legal protection</p> <p>* D4 averages the following indicators: 95. Access to employment 96. Access to social security and assistance 97. Access to housing</p>		
	<p>C.Children who received a final positive decision for Geneva Convention status by end of year (31 December) as a % of children with a pending decision during that year <i>Note: we will compare final decisions on 31 December YYYY with the total number of (1) children with pending decisions on 31 December YYYY-1 and (2) child asylum applicants during YYYY as measured on 31 December YYYY. "Children with pending decisions" means children whose application for international protection are under consideration by the responsible national authority at all instances of the administrative and/or judicial procedure. "Child asylum applicants" means children who have submitted an application for international protection or who have been included in such application as a family member during the reference period.</i></p> <p>Data source: Eurostat</p>	Eurostat	YES
D4.3 LPC access to education	<p>MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the dimension "Access to Education" (Education Strand) <i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>This MIPEX dimension aims to measure whether all children, with or without a legal status, have equal access to all levels of education *</p> <p>Source http://www.mipex.eu/education</p> <p>* The score in this dimension averages the following indicators 45. Compulsory education as legal right. Access is a legal right for all compulsory-age children in the country, regardless of their residence status (includes undocumented). Scores: 100 - Explicit obligation in law for all categories of migrants to have same access as nationals; 50 - Implicit obligation for all children (No impediment to equal access in law. e.g. No link between compulsory education and residence, or no category of migrant excluded); 0 - Restrictions in law on access for some categories of migrants 44. Access pre-primary and compulsory education: a. State-supported targeted measures (e.g. financial support, campaigns</p>	MIPEX policy indicators	YES

	<p>and other means) to increase participation of migrant pupils: b. Targeted measures to increase migrant pupils' successful completion of compulsory education (e.g. early school leaving/second chance programs). Scores: 100 - Both of these; 50 - One; 0 - None. Migrants only benefit from general support for all students (and targeted non-governmental initiatives where provided)</p> <p>46. Assessment of prior learning. The assessment in compulsory education of migrants' prior learning and language qualifications obtained abroad: a. Assessment with standardised quality criteria and tools; b. Requirement to use trained staff. Scores: 100- Both ; 50 - One; 0 - Case-by-case assessment by school staff without standardised criteria or training.</p> <p>47. Access to non-compulsory education is a legal right for all categories of migrants in the country, regardless of their residence status (includes undocumented). Scores: 100 - Explicit obligation in law for all categories of migrants to have same access as nationals.; 50 - Certain categories of migrants do not have explicit access to certain levels (e.g. vocational training and apprenticeships); 0 - Restrictions in law on access for some categories of migrants.</p> <p>48. Access to vocational training and training through apprenticeships or other work-based learning: a. Measures to specifically increase migrant pupil participation in such schemes (e.g. incentives); b. Measures to increase employers' supply of such schemes to migrant pupils (e.g. campaigns, support and guidance). Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - None. Migrants only benefit from general support. If there is targeted support for migrants, it is only through non-governmental initiatives</p> <p>49. Access to higher education: a. Targeted measures to increase migrant pupils' access to academic routes that lead to higher education; b. Targeted measures to increase acceptance and successful participation of migrant pupils (e.g. admission targets, additional targeted language support, mentoring, campaigns, measures to address drop-outs). Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - None. Migrants only benefit from general support. If there is targeted support for migrants, it is only through non-governmental initiatives</p>		
<p>D4.8 LPC access to health care</p>	<p>MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the policy strand Health <i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>MIPEX Health Strand aims to measure whether the health system is responsive to immigrants' needs. Its score averages the scores in the following policy dimensions: D1. Entitlement to health services (Are health entitlements equal for immigrants and for nationals?) * D2. Policies to facilitate access (Do policies assist immigrants in accessing their health entitlements?) * D3. Responsive health services (Are health services adapting to become more responsive to immigrants' needs?) * D4. Measures to achieve change (Does government support health services to become more responsive to immigrants' needs)*</p> <p>Source http://www.mipex.eu/health</p> <p>* D1 averages the following indicators: 151. Information for service providers about migrants' entitlements 152. Information for migrants concerning entitlements and use of health services (a. Methods of dissemination, b. Languages, c. Whether legal migrants, asylum seekers and undocumented migrants reached out) 153. Information for migrants concerning health education and</p>	<p>MIPEX policy indicators</p>	<p>YES</p>

	<p>promotion (a. Methods of dissemination, b. Languages, c. Whether legal migrants, asylum seekers and undocumented migrants reached out)</p> <p>154. Provision of 'cultural mediators' or 'patient navigators' to facilitate access for migrants</p> <p>155. Obligation and sanctions for assisting undocumented migrants (a. Obligation to report, b. Sanctions for helping)</p> <p>D2 averages the following indicators:</p> <p>145. Health entitlements for legal migrants (a. conditions for inclusion, b. extent of coverage, c. special exemptions)</p> <p>146. Health entitlements for asylum seekers (a. conditions for inclusion, b. extent of coverage, c. special exemptions)</p> <p>147. Health entitlements for undocumented migrants (a. conditions for inclusion, b. extent of coverage, c. special exemptions)</p> <p>148. Administrative discretion and documentation for legal migrants</p> <p>149. Administrative discretion and documentation for asylum seekers</p> <p>150. Administrative discretion and documentation for undocumented migrants</p> <p>D3 averages the following indicators:</p> <p>156. Availability of qualified interpretation services (a. Cost/availability of interpreters, b. Methods of interpretation)</p> <p>157. Requirement for 'culturally competent' or 'diversity-sensitive' services</p> <p>158. Training and education of health service staff</p> <p>159. Involvement of migrants in information provision, service design and delivery</p> <p>160. Encouraging diversity in the health service workforce</p> <p>161. Development of capacity and methods (a. Adapting methods, b. Specific methods)</p> <p>D4 averages the following indicators:</p> <p>162. Collection of data on migrant health</p> <p>163. Support for research on migrant health</p> <p>164. "Health in all policies" approach</p> <p>165. Whole organisation approach</p> <p>166. Leadership by government</p> <p>167. Involvement of migrants and stakeholders (a. stakeholders, b. migrants)</p>		
<p>D3.7.1 Concentration in disadvantaged schools</p>	<p>Difference in the share of migrant-background students and native students enrolled in disadvantaged schools</p> <p><i>Note: Disadvantaged schools are schools with a high concentration of students of low socio-economic status (25% or more, or 50% or more). The socio-economic status of families is the main predictor of educational disadvantage. Additionally, these schools tend to cumulate disadvantages (e.g. less resources, high teacher turnover, etc.). "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>Data source: survey data from PISA (15 years old), TIMSS (4th and 8th grade)</p>	<p>original</p>	<p>YES</p>
<p>D3.2.1 Clear leadership and school identity around intercultural values (against xenophobia, prejudice and stereotypes)</p>	<p>Arithmetic mean of principal and teachers' scores in the survey item below. The teachers' scores will be averaged</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 (for principals)</p> <p>How important are the following aspects for the identity of this school? (please, consider how it is presented to parents that approach the school for the first time)</p> <p>For each item: 1 Not very important 2 Somewhat important 3 Very important 4 This is one of our insignias</p> <p>a. Educational excellence and/or results</p> <p>b. Educational innovation</p> <p>c. Intercultural values (e.g. appreciation of diversity, cultural awareness, openness and tolerance)</p> <p>d. Other types of ethical values (e.g. religious, civiness,</p>	<p>original</p>	

	<p>etc.)</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 (for teachers) How important are the following aspects for the identity of this school? For each item: 1 Not very important 2 Somewhat important 3 Very important 4 This is one of our insignias a. Educational excellence and/or results b. Educational innovation c. Intercultural values (e.g. appreciation of diversity, cultural awareness, openness and tolerance) d. Other types of ethical values (e.g. religious, civicness, etc.)</p> <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from principals and teachers (IMMERSE)</p>		
<p>D3.2.3 School promotion of parental involvement in school activities, extra-curricular activities and parental associations</p>	<p>Average score in principals' answers to survey item below <i>Note: additionally, IMMERSE will collect information on parents' involvement in the same schools</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM (for principals) Does your school provide the following to students' parents? For each item: 1 No 2 Yes, generally for all parents 3 Yes, adapted for parents' needs (e.g. language, culture, etc.) a. Weekly (or more frequent) information on child's progress b. Requests and ideas to help students at home with homework c. Requests to volunteer and participate in school-related activities d. Channels to participate in decision-making</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM (for parents) During <the last academic year>, have you participated in any of the following school-related activities? For each item: 1 Yes 2 No 3 Not supported by school a. Attended a school meeting or met with the teachers b. Volunteered to support school activities (e.g. parent council, school garden, school play, guest speaker, assisted teachers, sports, field trip)</p> <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from parents (IMMERSE)</p>	<p>self-elaboration based on Epstein's framework and PISA</p>	
<p>D3.4.5 Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally</p>	<p>Arithmetic mean of principal and teachers' scores in the survey item below. The teachers' scores will be averaged</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 (for principals) Does the school curriculum include the following topics? For each item: Y/N Communicating with people from different cultures or countries Knowledge of different cultures Respect for cultural diversity Recognizing cultural prejudice and stereotypes</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 (for teachers) In your lessons, do you include opportunities to promote the following skills? For each item: Y/N Communicating with people from different cultures or countries Knowledge of different cultures Respect for cultural diversity</p>	<p>Adapted from PISA survey (Global Competence)</p>	

	<p>Recognizing cultural prejudice and stereotypes</p> <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from principals and teachers (IMMERSE)</p>		
<p>D4.15.5 LRR Intercultural education</p>	<p>MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the dimension "Intercultural Education For All" (Education Strand) <i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>This MIPEX dimension aims to measure whether all pupils and teachers are supported to learn and work together in a diverse society *</p> <p>Source http://www.mipex.eu/education</p> <p>* The score in this dimension averages the following indicators: 60. School curriculum to reflect diversity. The official aims of intercultural education include the appreciation of cultural diversity, and is delivered: a. As a stand-alone curriculum subject; b. Integrated throughout the curriculum. Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - Intercultural education not included in curriculum, or intercultural education does not include appreciation of cultural diversity 62. Adapting curriculum to reflect diversity. The school curricula and teaching materials can be modified to reflect changes in the diversity of the school population: a. State guidance on curricular change to reflect both national and local population variations; b. Inspection, evaluation and monitoring of implementation of (a). Scores: 100 - Both of these; 50 - One of these; 0 - None. 61. State support for public information initiatives to promote the appreciation of cultural diversity throughout society. Scores: 100 - Initiatives part of mandate of state-subsidised bod; 50 - Initiatives part of state budget line for ad hoc funding; 0 - Neither 63. Adapting daily school life to reflect diversity. Daily life at school can be adapted based on cultural or religious needs in order to avoid exclusion of pupils, which might include one or a few of the following: changes to the existing school timetable and religious holidays; educational activities; dress codes and clothing; school menus. Scores: 100 - State regulations or guidelines concerning local adaptation; 50 - Law allows for local or school-level discretion; 0 - No specific adaptation foreseen in law. 64. Teacher training to reflect diversity. Teacher training and professional development programmes require intercultural education and the appreciation of cultural diversity for all teachers: a. topic in pre-service training in order to qualify as a teacher; b. topic in obligatory in-service professional development training. Scores: 100 - Both A and B required; 50 - Both offered extensively; 0 - only ad hoc/ project basis</p>	<p>MIPEX policy indicators</p>	<p>YES</p>
<p>D3.3.3 Low expectations / stereotypes among teachers towards certain groups</p>	<p>Weighted average of teachers' answers and (all) children's answers to survey items below <i>Note: the weighted average will provide a larger weight to teachers' answers, based on the assumption that teachers are in a better position to assess their fellow teachers' biases. Children may both underestimate and overestimate to a larger extent, but it is important to include their perceptions, inasmuch those perceptions mediate the impact that actual low expectations have in children's performance.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 (for teachers) Thinking about teachers in your school: to how many of them do the following statements apply? For each item: None or almost none of them 1, Some of them 2, Most of them 3, All or almost all of them 4 - They have lower academic expectations for students of</p>	<p>Adapted from PISA survey (global competence)</p>	

	<p>some groups - They say negative things about people of some groups Note: "groups" refers to any relevant social categories (ethnicity, religion, culture, social class, etc.)</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 (for children) Thinking about teachers in your school: to how many of them do the following statements apply? For each item: None or almost none of them 1, Some of them 2, Most of them 3, All or almost all of them 4 - They have lower academic expectations for students of some groups - They say negative things about people of some groups Note: "groups" refers to categories that people frequently use (e.g. ethnic groups, cultural groups, social groups, etc.)</p> <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE). This question will not be asked to children 6-10</p>		
<p>D4.16.1 LRR Preparatory classes</p>	<p>Whether there are provisions of preparatory classes for newly arrived migrant students at state or national level <i>Note: Preparatory classes – in some countries also referred to as 'reception classes' or 'transition classes' – are separate classes or lessons in which newly arrived migrant students are provided with intensive language teaching and, in some cases, an adapted curriculum for other subjects with the intention of preparing them to integrate into mainstream classes. Students maybe placed in these classes/lessons full time or combine these classes/ lessons with mainstream ones (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2017).</i></p> <p>Source: Eurydice 2019 and subsequent reports.</p> <p>We will cross-check, complement and update this data with survey data collected by IMMERSE from principals (survey item below).</p> <p>Are there provisions or recommendations at the regional or national level to offer preparatory classes for newly arrived migrant students? 1 Yes, at national level 2 Yes, at regional level 3 Yes, at both national and regional levels 2 No</p> <p>Does this school offer preparatory classes for newly arrived migrant students? 1 Yes 2 No</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from principals (IMMERSE).</p>	<p>Original inspired by Eurydice 2017</p>	<p>YES</p>
<p>D4.16.2 LRR Educational support for migrant children, particularly learning and language support</p>	<p>MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the dimension "Targeting needs" (Education Strand) <i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>This MIPEX dimension aims to measure whether migrant</p>	<p>MIPEX policy indicators</p>	<p>YES</p>

	<p>children, as well as their parents and teachers, are entitled to have their specific needs addressed in school *</p> <p>Source http://www.mipex.eu/education</p> <p>* The score in this dimension averages the following indicators: 50. Educational guidance. Access to advice and guidance on system and choices at all levels of compulsory and non-compulsory education (pre-primary to higher): a. Written information on educational system in migrant languages of origin; b. Provision of resource persons/centres for orientation of migrant pupils; c. Provision of interpretation services for families of migrant pupils for general educational advice and guidance at all levels. Scores: 100 - All three ; 50 - one or two; 0 - Migrants only benefit from general support. If there is targeted support for migrants, it is only through non-governmental initiatives. 51. Provision of support to learn language of instruction (average 51a-51c) 51a. Language instruction. Provision of continuous and ongoing education support in language(s) of instruction for migrant pupils: a. In compulsory education (both primary and secondary); b. In pre-primary education. Note: Migrant pupils may be placed in the mainstream classroom or a separate classroom for a transitional phase. This question relates to language support in either case. Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - No provision. Only through private or community initiatives 51b. Communicative/academic fluency. Provision includes: a. Communicative literacy (general fluency in reading, writing, and communicating in the language); b. Academic literacy (fluency in studying, researching, and communicating in the language in the school academic setting). Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - Level/goals not specified or defined 51c. Language instruction standards. Provision includes quality measures: a. Requirement for courses to use established second-language learning standards; b. Requirement for teachers to be specialised and certified in these standards; c. Curriculum standards are monitored by a state body. Scores: 100 - Two or more of these; 50 - At least one; 0 - None of these 52. Migrant pupil monitoring. Policy on pupil monitoring targets migrants. Scores: 100 - System disaggregates migrants into various sub-groups, e.g. gender, country of origin; 50 - System monitors migrants as a single aggregated group; 0 - None. Migrants are only included in general categories for monitoring that apply to all students. 53. Targeted policies to address educational situation of migrant groups: a. Systematic provision of guidance (e.g. teaching assistance, homework support); b. Systematic provision of financial resources. Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - None. Migrants only benefit from general support. If there is targeted support for migrants, it is only through voluntary initiative 54. Teacher training and professional development programmes require courses that address migrant pupils' learning needs, teachers' expectations of migrant pupils, and specific teaching strategies to address this: a. Topic required in pre-service training in order to qualify as a teacher; b. Topic required in obligatory in-service professional development training. Scores: 100 - Both required; 50 - Both offered extensively to teachers; 0 - only on ad hoc / project basis.</p>		
<p>D5.6 Supplementary community services for learning/ language support</p>	<p>Difference in the share of migrant-background children and native children who pick answer #1 in at least one of survey items below</p> <p><i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p>	<p>original</p>	

	<p>SURVEY ITEM 1 Are there services in your school providing learning support for students after school hours (to help them with homework, language learning, etc.) and that you can access ?</p> <p>1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there is nothing I can afford / access 4 No, there are no such services at all 5 I don't know</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 Are there services in your <community / neighbourhood> providing learning support for students (to help them with homework, language learning, etc.) and that you can access ?</p> <p>1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there is nothing I can afford / access 4 No, there are no such services at all 5 I don't know</p> <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE). The question will be adapted for age 6-10</p>		
<p>D3.5.4 Extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres</p>	<p>Difference in the share of migrant-background children and native children who pick answer #1 in at least one of survey items below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 Are there extra-curricular activities (such as sports, arts, music, additional languages, etc.) in your school that you can access ?</p> <p>1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there is nothing I can access 4 No, there are no such services at all 5 I don't know</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 Are there extra-curricular activities (such as sports, arts, music, additional languages, etc.) in your <community / neighbourhood> that you can access ?</p> <p>1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there is nothing I can access 4 No, there are no such services at all 5 I don't know</p> <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE). The question will be adapted for age 6-10</p>	<p>original</p>	
<p>D3.6.2 Counselling services at school</p>	<p>Share of schools with some staff dedicated to psycho-social support or personal counselling, based on survey item below</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM How many staff does your school currently have in the following capacities? Please note this refers to staff hired specifically to conduct these tasks, which usually requires</p>	<p>original</p>	

	<p>some specific training. For each category: Nr full time: __ Nr part time: ____</p> <p>a. Language support teachers b. Learning support teachers (exclude the ones counted in a.) c. Psycho-social support / personal counselling d. Academic counselling / guidance (exclude the ones counted in c.)</p> <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from principals (IMMERSE)</p>		
<p>D3.3.4 Diversity among teachers and school personnel</p>	<p>Share of schools (principals) that respond positively (yes) to survey item below</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM Does this school employ teachers of more than one cultural or ethnic background? Y/N If yes: Could you tell me approximately in which proportion? Less than 10% from 10 to 25% From 25% to 50% Over 50%</p> <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from principals (IMMERSE)</p>	<p>original</p>	
<p>D6.1 Experience/perception of negative attitudes</p>	<p>A1. National-level indicator: average score for survey item below</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM Is [survey country] made a worse or a better place to live by people coming to live here from other countries? Choose on from worse place to live 0 to better place to live 10</p> <p>Data source: European Social Survey (ESS)</p> <p>A2. Local-level indicator: arithmetic mean of teachers' average score and native students' average score in survey item below <i>Note: "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey</i></p> <p>Is [country] made a worse or a better place to live by people coming to live here from other countries? Choose on from worse place to live 0 to better place to live 10</p> <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from teachers and children (IMMERSE). This question won't be applied to children aged 6-10.</p> <p>B. Difference in the share of migrant-background children and native children who answer positively to survey item below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM Do you avoid certain places (such as shops, cafes, public</p>	<p>ESS survey</p>	<p>YES</p>
		<p>Original adapted from UK Household Longitudinal Study</p>	

	<p>transportation or some particular neighbourhood) for fear of being treated badly? Y/N IF YES Is the reason for this related to any of the issues below? (multiple option) 1 Your culture, religion or ethnicity 2 Your gender 3 Your sexual orientation 4 Your age 5 Your social class 6 Other</p> <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE). This question won't be applied to children aged 6-10.</p>		
<p>D6.2 Experience of harassment and/or physical violence (incl. bullying) outside family</p>	<p>Difference in share of migrant-background children and native children responding 2-5 in the survey item below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>Have you been bullied at school or by schoolmates in your <neighbourhood> or in the cyberspace in the past couple of months? 1 I have not been bullied 2 It has only happened once or twice 3 It has happened 2 or 3 times a month 4 About once a week 5 Several times a week</p> <p>Data source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE)</p>	<p>Based on HBSC</p>	

Annex 7. Final IMMERSE dashboard of indicators

#	FACTOR	FINAL VERSION	Reference source	Re-utilize	Data collection
1	01.2.1 Children's access to compulsory education	<p>Scholarization rates. Proxied by: foreign children enrolled at school as a share of foreign children in compulsory ages</p> <p><i>Note: we use citizenship (foreign children) as a proxy of migrant-background (country of birth and parents' country of birth) because data on school enrolment is more often available by citizenship than by migration-background (country of birth and parents' country of birth)</i></p> <p>Source: administrative data and Eurostat</p>	original	YES	
2	01.2.3 Children's access to health care	<p>Difference in share of migrant-background and native respondents with children under 16 that had unmet needs for medical examination in the last 12 months</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM</p> <p>Was there any time during the past 12 months when [any of] your child[ren] (aged 0-15) really needed medical examination or treatment (excluding dental examination or treatment)? Y/N</p> <p>[If yes] Did your child[ren] have a medical examination or treatment each time it was really needed? Y/N</p> <p>[If yes] What was the main reason for not having a medical examination or treatment?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Could not afford to (too expensive) 2. Waiting list or the time needed to obtain an appointment was too long 3. Could not take the time because of work, care of other children or of other persons 4. Too far to travel or no means of transportation 5. Other reason <p>Source: EU-SILC survey (ad hoc module every 5 years, last in 2017).</p>	EU-SILC survey	YES	(children 10+)
3	02.1.1 Children's perceived competence in host language	<p>Average score of migrant/background students in the survey items below</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM</p> <p>Imagine the following situations:</p> <p>A. You need to ask your teacher for some information in <main language>. Can you explain yourself?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Almost never 2 Sometimes 3 Almost always <p>B. When your teacher gives you some information in <main language>. Can you understand?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Almost never 2 Sometimes 3 Almost always <p>This question will be adapted to <u>children aged 6-9</u></p>	original		Children, adapted for 6-9

		<p>as follows</p> <p>A. When I need to ask my teacher for some information in <main language> I can explain myself. 1 Almost never 2 Sometimes 3 Almost always</p> <p>B. When my teacher gives me some information in <main language> I can understand. 1 Almost never 2 Sometimes 3 Almost always</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE).</p>			
<p>4</p>	<p>O2.2.2 Children maintain their cultural identity while adopting key host country cultural values and intercultural competences</p>	<p>Share of migrant background children picking the following combinations in the survey item below</p> <p>a. Some of 1-4; and also some of 5-7 b. Some of 1-4; and not 5-7 c. Some of 5-7; and not 1-4 d. Only options 8-10; none from 1-7</p> <p>A. Do you feel close to the following groups? (for example: groups of friends, classmates, neighbours, etc.) For each group: Y/N</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. People from your neighbourhood 2. People from [City where they live] 3. [People from Host country] (i.e. Germans, Irish, Spaniards...) 4. People working at your school (i.e. teachers, other employees...) 5. People from [children/parents' country/ies of origin*] 6. People with your same home language 7. People with your same religion 8. People of your same age 9. People of your same gender 10. People with your same interests and hobbies <p>B. Choose the three groups from question A to which you feel closest to and rank them 1st to 3rd:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 2. 3. <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE). This question <u>will not be asked to children aged 6-9</u></p>	<p>original</p>		<p>Children 10+</p>
<p>5</p>	<p>O3.1.2 Children's life satisfaction / happiness</p>	<p>Difference in share of migrant-background children and native children that pick options 1-2 in survey item below</p> <p><i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage)</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM In general, would you say you are: 1 Very happy</p>	<p>EVS</p>		<p>Children, adapted 6-9</p>

		<p>2 Quite happy 3 Not very happy 4 Not at all happy</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE)</p>			
6	03.1.3 Children's sense of belonging	<p>Average score in the survey items below among migrant-background children <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage)</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM How frequently do the following occur to you? For each item: 1 Almost never, 2 Sometimes, 3 Almost always I feel like I belong at my school I can really be myself at school I feel like people at my school care about me</p> <p><i>Note: the selected indicator focuses on school belonging acknowledging the centrality of schools for the integration of migrant-children in general, and for their sense of belonging in the host country in particular</i></p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE)</p>	Student subjective wellbeing questionnaire (School connectedness subscale)		Children, adapted 6-9
7	04.1.1 Interconnectedness / Friends and peers	<p>A. Difference in the average score of migrant-background children and native children in the items below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM Do the following sentences happen to you? For each item: 1 Almost never, 2 Sometimes, 3 Almost always - My friends really try to help me - I can talk with my friends about what makes me happy and sad - My friends stand up for me if someone mistreats me</p> <p>This question will be adapted to <u>children aged 6-9</u> as follows:</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM Do the following sentences happen to you? For each item: 1 Almost never, 2 Sometimes, 3 Almost always - My friends really try to help me - I can talk with my friends about what makes me happy and sad - My friends stand up for me if someone is mean to me</p>	HBSC survey		Children, adapted 6-9

		<p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE)</p>			
<p>8</p>	<p>04.1.1 Interconnectedness / Friends and peers</p>	<p>B. Share of all children (migrant-background and native) selecting option #1 in both survey items below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM How many of your friends were born in a different country than yours? 1 All of them 2 The majority of them 3 A few 4 None 5 Don't have any friends</p> <p>How many of your friends are from a different culture (beliefs, customs, traditions, ways of eating...)? 1 All of them 2 The majority of them 3 A few 4 None 5 Don't have any friends</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE). This question <u>will not be asked to children 6-9</u></p>	<p>Community Life Survey UK</p>		<p>Children 10+</p>
<p>9</p>	<p>04.1.2 Interconnectedness / Teachers</p>	<p>Difference in average score between migrant-background and native children in the survey items below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM How frequently do the following occur to you? For each item: 1 Almost never, 2 Sometimes, 3 Almost always - My teachers really try to help me - Most of my teachers really listen to what I have to say - My teachers will stand up for me if someone mistreats me</p> <p>This question will be adapted to <u>children aged 6-9</u> as follows:</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM Do the following sentences happen to you? For each item: 1 Almost never, 2 Sometimes, 3 Almost always</p>	<p>ICCS survey</p>		<p>Children, adapted 6-9</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - My teachers really try to help me - Most of my teachers really listen to what I have to say - My teachers will stand up for me if someone is mean to me <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE).</p>			
10	04.1.3 Interconnectedness / Institutions	<p>Difference in average score between migrant-background and native children in the survey items below</p> <p><i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM</p> <p>In [host country], do you trust the following?</p> <p>For each item: yes or no</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Teachers and schools b. Doctors and hospitals c. Police & justice system (judges, lawyers, courts, etc.) <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE).</p>	original		Children, adapted 6-9
11	05.1.1 Children's academic skills	<p>Difference in the share of low achievers in reading, mathematics and science among migrant-background and native children (15-year-olds)</p> <p><i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>Source: PISA</p>	PISA survey	YES	
12	05.2.1 Children complete compulsory education	<p>Share of persons with compulsory education completed among foreign-born population aged 16-20 who arrived in the host country before age 15</p> <p><i>Note: the limit of 16 refers to the start of non-compulsory age, and shall be adapted accordingly in countries with a different limit</i></p> <p>Source: PIAAC</p>	PIAAC survey	YES	
13	05.2.2 Children remain in formal education beyond compulsory levels	<p>Difference in share of early leavers among foreign-born and non-foreign born persons aged 18-24</p> <p><i>Note: "Early leaver from education and training" refers to a person aged 18 to 24 who has completed at most lower secondary education (<INSERT HERE THE CORRESPONDING LABEL IN YOUR NATIONAL EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM >) and is not involved in further education or training (formal or informal)</i></p>	Eurostat/EU-LFS	YES	

		Source: Eurostat/EU-LFS		
14	05.2.3 Types and levels of (formal) non-compulsory education attended	<p>Difference in share of foreign-born and non-foreign born population aged 16-24 who have completed (or are currently studying) upper secondary or tertiary studies in the survey country <i>Note: the limit of 16 refers to the start of non-compulsory age, and shall be adapted accordingly in countries with a different limit</i></p> <p>Source: PIAAC (2011/2, next in 2021/2; unavailable in Greece and French community in Belgium)</p>	PIAAC survey	YES
15	D4.2 Legislation and practice conditioning (LPC) the acquisition of superior legal status	<p>A. MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the policy strand Access to Nationality <i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>MIPEX Access to Nationality Strand aims to measure whether legal immigrants are encouraged to naturalise and whether their children born in the country are entitled to become full citizens. Its score averages the scores in the following policy dimensions: D1. Eligibility (How long must migrants wait to naturalise? Are their children and grandchildren born in the country entitled to become citizens?) * D2. Conditions for acquisition (Are applicants encouraged to succeed through basic conditions for naturalisation?)* D3. Security status (Does the state protect applicants from discretionary procedures?) * D4. Dual nationality (Can naturalising migrants and their children be citizens of more than one country?) *</p> <p>Source: http://www.mipex.eu/access-nationality</p> <p>* D1 averages the following indicators: 98. Residence period 99. Permits considered 100. Periods of prior-absence allowed 101. Requirements for spouses and partners (a. Spouses of nationals, b. partners of nationals, c. special exemptions) 102. Birth-right citizenship for second generation 103. Birth-right citizenship for third generation</p> <p>* D2 averages the following indicators: 104. Naturalisation language requirement (a. level, b. exemption, c. cost, d. support, e. courses) 105. Naturalisation integration requirement (a. form, b. exemption, c. cost, d. support, e. courses) 106. Economic resources 107. Criminal record 108. Good character</p>	MIPEX policy indicators	YES

	<p>109. Cost of application</p> <p>* D3 averages the following indicators: 110. Maximum duration of procedure 111. Additional grounds for refusal 112. Discretionary powers in refusal 113. Legal protection 114. Protection against withdrawal of citizenship (a. grounds, time limits, statelessness protections)</p> <p>* D4 averages the following indicators: 115. Dual nationality for first generation (a. Renunciation requirement; b. Renunciation exemptions) 116. Dual nationality for second/third generation (at birth or before majority, facilitated, not facilitated)</p>			
<p>16</p> <p>D4.2 Legislation and practice conditioning (LPC) the acquisition of superior legal status</p>	<p>B. MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the policy strand Access to Permanent Residence <i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>MIPEX Access to Permanent Residence aims to measure whether temporary legal residents have facilitated access to a long-term residence permit. Its score averages the scores in the following policy dimensions: D1. Eligibility (Can all temporary legal residents apply for a long-term residence permit?)* D2. Conditions for acquisition (Do applicants for long-term residence have to fulfil the same basic conditions in society?)* D3. Security status (Does the state protect applicants from discretionary procedures?)* D4. Rights associated with status (Do long-term residents have the same residence and socio-economic rights?)*</p> <p>Source: http://www.mipex.eu/permanent-residence</p> <p>* D1 averages the following indicators: 80. Residence period 81. Permits considered 82. Time counted as pupil/student 83. Periods of prior-absence allowed</p> <p>* D2 averages the following indicators: 84. Language requirement 85. Economic resources 86. Cost of application</p> <p>* D3 averages the following indicators: 87. Maximum duration of procedure 88. Duration of validity of permit 89. Renewable permit</p>	<p>MIPEX policy indicators</p>	<p>YES</p>	

		<p>90. Periods of absence allowed 91. Grounds for rejection, withdrawal, refusal 92. Personal circumstances considered before expulsion 93. Expulsion precluded 94. Legal protection</p> <p>* D4 averages the following indicators: 95. Access to employment 96. Access to social security and assistance 97. Access to housing</p>			
17	D4.3 LPC access to education	<p>MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the dimension "Access to Education" (Education Strand) <i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>This MIPEX dimension aims to measure whether all children, with or without a legal status, have equal access to all levels of education *</p> <p>Source http://www.mipex.eu/education</p> <p>* The score in this dimension averages the following indicators</p> <p>45. Compulsory education as legal right. Access is a legal right for all compulsory-age children in the country, regardless of their residence status (includes undocumented). Scores: 100 - Explicit obligation in law for all categories of migrants to have same access as nationals; 50 - Implicit obligation for all children (No impediment to equal access in law. e.g. No link between compulsory education and residence, or no category of migrant excluded); 0 - Restrictions in law on access for some categories of migrants</p> <p>44. Access pre-primary and compulsory education: a. State-supported targeted measures (e.g. financial support, campaigns and other means) to increase participation of migrant pupils: b. Targeted measures to increase migrant pupils' successful completion of compulsory education (e.g. early school leaving/second chance programs). Scores: 100 - Both of these; 50 - One; 0 - None. Migrants only benefit from general support for all students (and targeted non-governmental initiatives where provided)</p> <p>46. Assessment of prior learning. The assessment in compulsory education of migrants' prior learning and language qualifications obtained abroad: a. Assessment with standardised quality criteria and tools; b. Requirement to use trained staff. Scores: 100- Both ; 50 - One; 0 - Case-by-case assessment by school staff without standardised criteria or training.</p> <p>47. Access to non-compulsory education is a legal right for all categories of migrants in the country, regardless of their residence status (includes</p>	MIPEX policy indicators	YES	

		<p>undocumented). Scores: 100 - Explicit obligation in law for all categories of migrants to have same access as nationals; 50 - Certain categories of migrants do not have explicit access to certain levels (e.g. vocational training and apprenticeships); 0 - Restrictions in law on access for some categories of migrants.</p> <p>48. Access to vocational training and training through apprenticeships or other work-based learning: a. Measures to specifically increase migrant pupil participation in such schemes (e.g. incentives); b. Measures to increase employers' supply of such schemes to migrant pupils (e.g. campaigns, support and guidance). Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - None. Migrants only benefit from general support. If there is targeted support for migrants, it is only through non-governmental initiatives</p> <p>49. Access to higher education: a. Targeted measures to increase migrant pupils' access to academic routes that lead to higher education; b. Targeted measures to increase acceptance and successful participation of migrant pupils (e.g. admission targets, additional targeted language support, mentoring, campaigns, measures to address drop-outs). Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - None. Migrants only benefit from general support. If there is targeted support for migrants, it is only through non-governmental initiatives</p>			
<p>18</p>	<p>D4.8 LPC access to health care</p>	<p>MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the policy strand Health <i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>MIPEX Health Strand aims to measure whether the health system is responsive to immigrants' needs. Its score averages the scores in the following policy dimensions: D1. Entitlement to health services (Are health entitlements equal for immigrants and for nationals?) * D2. Policies to facilitate access (Do policies assist immigrants in accessing their health entitlements?) * D3. Responsive health services (Are health services adapting to become more responsive to immigrants' needs?) * D4. Measures to achieve change (Does government support health services to become more responsive to immigrants' needs?)*</p> <p>Source: http://www.mipex.eu/health</p> <p>* D1 averages the following indicators: 151. Information for service providers about migrants' entitlements 152. Information for migrants concerning</p>	<p>MIPEX policy indicators</p>	<p>YES</p>	

		<p>entitlements and use of health services (a. Methods of dissemination, b. Languages, c. Whether legal migrants, asylum seekers and undocumented migrants reached out)</p> <p>153. Information for migrants concerning health education and promotion (a. Methods of dissemination, b. Languages, c. Whether legal migrants, asylum seekers and undocumented migrants reached out)</p> <p>154. Provision of 'cultural mediators' or 'patient navigators' to facilitate access for migrants</p> <p>155. Obligation and sanctions for assisting undocumented migrants (a. Obligation to report, b. Sanctions for helping)</p> <p>* D2 averages the following indicators:</p> <p>145. Health entitlements for legal migrants (a. conditions for inclusion, b. extent of coverage, c. special exemptions)</p> <p>146. Health entitlements for asylum seekers (a. conditions for inclusion, b. extent of coverage, c. special exemptions)</p> <p>147. Health entitlements for undocumented migrants (a. conditions for inclusion, b. extent of coverage, c. special exemptions)</p> <p>148. Administrative discretion and documentation for legal migrants</p> <p>149. Administrative discretion and documentation for asylum seekers</p> <p>150. Administrative discretion and documentation for undocumented migrants</p> <p>* D3 averages the following indicators:</p> <p>156. Availability of qualified interpretation services (a. Cost/availability of interpreters, b. Methods of interpretation)</p> <p>157. Requirement for 'culturally competent' or 'diversity-sensitive' services</p> <p>158. Training and education of health service staff</p> <p>159. Involvement of migrants in information provision, service design and delivery</p> <p>160. Encouraging diversity in the health service workforce</p> <p>161. Development of capacity and methods (a. Adapting methods, b. Specific methods)</p> <p>* D4 averages the following indicators:</p> <p>162. Collection of data on migrant health</p> <p>163. Support for research on migrant health</p> <p>164. "Health in all policies" approach</p> <p>165. Whole organisation approach</p> <p>166. Leadership by government</p> <p>167. Involvement of migrants and stakeholders (a. stakeholders, b. migrants)</p>			
19	<p>D3.7.1 Concentration in disadvantaged schools</p>	<p>Difference in the share of migrant-background students and native students enrolled in disadvantaged schools</p> <p><i>Note: Disadvantaged schools are schools with a high concentration of students of low socio-economic status (25% or more, or 50% or more). The socio-economic status of families is the</i></p>	original	YES	

		<p><i>main predictor of educational disadvantage. Additionally, these schools tend to cumulate disadvantages (e.g. less resources, high teacher turnover, etc.). "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>Source: survey data from PISA (15 years old), TIMSS (4th and 8th grade)</p>		
20	<p>D3.2.1 Clear leadership and school identity around intercultural values (against xenophobia, prejudice and stereotypes)</p>	<p>Arithmetic mean of principal and teachers' scores in the survey item below. The teachers' scores will be averaged</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 (for principals) How important are the following aspects for this school? (please, consider how it is presented to parents that approach the school for the first time) For each item: 1 Not very important 2 Somewhat important 3 Very important 4 This is one of our insignias a. Educational excellence and/or results b. Educational innovation c. Intercultural values (e.g. appreciation of diversity, cultural awareness, openness and tolerance) d. Other types of ethical values (e.g. religious, civicism, etc.)</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 (for teachers) How important are the following aspects for this school? For each item: 1 Not very important 2 Somewhat important 3 Very important 4 This is one of our insignias a. Educational excellence and/or results b. Educational innovation c. Intercultural values (e.g. appreciation of diversity, cultural awareness, openness and tolerance) d. Other types of ethical values (e.g. religious, civicism, etc.)</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from principals and teachers (IMMERSE)</p>	original	Teachers & principals
21	<p>D3.2.3 School promotion of parental involvement in school activities, extra-curricular activities and parental associations</p>	<p>Average score in principals' answers to survey item below <i>Note: additionally, IMMERSE will collect information on parents' involvement in the same schools</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM (for principals) Does your school provide the following to students' parents? For each item: 1 No 2 Yes, generally for all parents 3 Yes, adapted for parents' needs (e.g. language, culture, etc.) a. Weekly (or more frequent) information on</p>	self-elaboration based on Epstein's framework and PISA	Principals

		<p>child's progress</p> <p>b. Requests and ideas to help students at home with homework</p> <p>c. Requests to volunteer and participate in school-related activities</p> <p>d. Channels to participate in decision-making</p> <p>Source: self-elaboration based on Epstein's framework and PISA.</p>			
22	D3.4.5 Intercultural competence as part of syllabus or/and transversally	<p>Arithmetic mean of principal and teachers' scores in the survey item below. The teachers' scores will be averaged</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 (for principals) Does the school curriculum include the following topics? For each item: Y/N Communicating with people from different cultures or countries Knowledge of different cultures Respect for cultural diversity Recognizing cultural prejudice and stereotypes</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 (for teachers) In your lessons, do you include opportunities to promote the following skills? For each item: Y/N Communicating with people from different cultures or countries Knowledge of different cultures Respect for cultural diversity Recognizing cultural prejudice and stereotypes</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from principals and teachers (IMMERSE)</p>	PISA survey		Teachers & principals
23	D4.15.5 LRR Intercultural education	<p>MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the dimension "Intercultural Education For All" (Education Strand)</p> <p><i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>This MIPEX dimension aims to measure whether all pupils and teachers are supported to learn and work together in a diverse society *</p> <p>Source http://www.mipex.eu/education</p> <p>* The score in this dimension averages the following indicators: 60. School curriculum to reflect diversity. The official aims of intercultural education include the appreciation of cultural diversity, and is delivered: a. As a stand-alone curriculum subject; b. Integrated throughout the curriculum. Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - Intercultural education not included in curriculum, or intercultural education does not include appreciation of cultural diversity</p>	MIPEX policy indicators	YES	

		<p>62. Adapting curriculum to reflect diversity. The school curricula and teaching materials can be modified to reflect changes in the diversity of the school population: a. State guidance on curricular change to reflect both national and local population variations; b. Inspection, evaluation and monitoring of implementation of (a). Scores: 100 - Both of these; 50 - One of these; 0 - None.</p> <p>61. State support for public information initiatives to promote the appreciation of cultural diversity throughout society. Scores: 100 - Initiatives part of mandate of state-subsidised bod; 50 - Initiatives part of state budget line for ad hoc funding; 0 - Neither</p> <p>63. Adapting daily school life to reflect diversity. Daily life at school can be adapted based on cultural or religious needs in order to avoid exclusion of pupils, which might include one or a few of the following: changes to the existing school timetable and religious holidays; educational activities; dress codes and clothing; school menus. Scores: 100 - State regulations or guidelines concerning local adaptation; 50 - Law allows for local or school-level discretion; 0 - No specific adaptation foreseen in law.</p> <p>64. Teacher training to reflect diversity. Teacher training and professional development programmes require intercultural education and the appreciation of cultural diversity for all teachers: a. topic in pre-service training in order to qualify as a teacher; b. topic in obligatory in-service professional development training. Scores: 100 - Both A and B required; 50 - Both offered extensively; 0 - only ad hoc/ project basis</p>			
<p>24</p>	<p>D4.16.1 LRR Preparatory classes</p>	<p>Whether there are provisions of preparatory classes for newly arrived migrant students at state or national level <i>Note: Preparatory classes – in some countries also referred to as 'reception classes' or 'transition classes' – are separate classes or lessons in which newly arrived migrant students are provided with intensive language teaching and, in some cases, an adapted curriculum for other subjects with the intention of preparing them to integrate into mainstream classes. Students may be placed in these classes/lessons full time or combine these classes/ lessons with mainstream ones (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2017).</i></p> <p>Source: Eurydice 2019 and subsequent reports.</p> <p>We will cross-check, complement and update this data with survey data collected by IMMERSE from principals (survey item below).</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM Are there provisions or recommendations at the regional or national level to offer preparatory classes for newly arrived migrant students? 1 Yes, at national level 2 Yes, at regional level</p>	<p>Eurydice 2019</p>	<p>YES</p>	<p>(Principals)</p>

		<p>3 Yes, at both national and regional levels 4 No</p> <p>Does this school offer preparatory classes for newly arrived migrant students? 1 Yes 2 No</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from principals (IMMERSE).</p>			
<p>25</p>	<p>D4.16.2 LRR Educational support for migrant children, particularly learning and language support</p>	<p>MIPEX policy score (0-100) for the dimension "Targeting needs" (Education Strand) <i>Note: The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) measures policies to integrate migrants in all EU Member States and other countries since 2007. Policy experts in each country evaluate 167 indicators, which are grouped into dimensions, also grouped into 8 policy areas (Strands).</i></p> <p>This MIPEX dimension aims to measure whether migrant children, as well as their parents and teachers, are entitled to have their specific needs addressed in school *</p> <p>Source: http://www.mipex.eu/education</p> <p>* The score in this dimension averages the following indicators: 50. Educational guidance. Access to advice and guidance on system and choices at all levels of compulsory and non-compulsory education (pre-primary to higher): a. Written information on educational system in migrant languages of origin; b. Provision of resource persons/centres for orientation of migrant pupils; c. Provision of interpretation services for families of migrant pupils for general educational advice and guidance at all levels. Scores: 100 - All three ; 50 - one or two; 0 - Migrants only benefit from general support. If there is targeted support for migrants, it is only through non-governmental initiatives. 51. Provision of support to learn language of instruction (average 51a-51c) 51a. Language instruction. Provision of continuous and ongoing education support in language(s) of instruction for migrant pupils: a. In compulsory education (both primary and secondary); b. In pre-primary education. Note: Migrant pupils may be placed in the mainstream classroom or a separate classroom for a transitional phase. This question relates to language support in either case. Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - No provision. Only through private or community initiatives 51b. Communicative/academic fluency. Provision includes: a. Communicative literacy (general fluency in reading, writing, and communicating in the language); b. Academic literacy (fluency in studying, researching, and communicating in the language in the school academic setting). Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - Level/goals not specified</p>	<p>MIPEX policy indicators</p>	<p>YES</p>	

		<p>or defined</p> <p>51c. Language instruction standards. Provision includes quality measures: a. Requirement for courses to use established second-language learning standards; b. Requirement for teachers to be specialised and certified in these standards; c. Curriculum standards are monitored by a state body. Scores: 100 - Two or more of these; 50 - At least one; 0 - None of these</p> <p>52. Migrant pupil monitoring. Policy on pupil monitoring targets migrants. Scores: 100 - System disaggregates migrants into various sub-groups, e.g. gender, country of origin; 50 - System monitors migrants as a single aggregated group; 0 - None. Migrants are only included in general categories for monitoring that apply to all students.</p> <p>53. Targeted policies to address educational situation of migrant groups: a. Systematic provision of guidance (e.g. teaching assistance, homework support); b. Systematic provision of financial resources. Scores: 100 - Both; 50 - One; 0 - None. Migrants only benefit from general support. If there is targeted support for migrants, it is only through voluntary initiative</p> <p>54. Teacher training and professional development programmes require courses that address migrant pupils' learning needs, teachers' expectations of migrant pupils, and specific teaching strategies to address this: a. Topic required in pre-service training in order to qualify as a teacher; b. Topic required in obligatory in-service professional development training. Scores: 100 - Both required; 50 - Both offered extensively to teachers; 0 - only on ad hoc / project basis.</p>			
<p>26</p>	<p>D5.6 Supplementary community services for learning/ language support</p>	<p>Difference in the share of migrant-background children and native children who pick answer #1 in at least one of survey items below</p> <p><i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 Are there services in your school providing learning support for students after school hours (to help them with homework, language learning, etc.)? 1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there is nothing I can afford / access 4 No, there are no such services at all 5 I don't know</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 Are there services in your <community / neighbourhood> providing learning support for students (to help them with homework, language</p>	<p>original</p>		<p>Children, adapted 6-9</p>

		<p>learning, etc.) ? 1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there is nothing I can afford / access 4 No, there are no such services at all 5 I don't know</p> <p>This question will be adapted to <u>children aged 6-9</u> as follows:</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 Do you take any classes at school to help you with your schoolwork or learn new languages, but are not part of your normal school day (after class)? 1 Yes, I do take classes 2 My school has those, but I don't take classes 3 No, my school doesn't have those 4 I don't know</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 Do you take any classes (outside of school) in your neighbourhood (where you live) to help you with school work or learn new languages ? 1 Yes, I do take classes 2 My neighbourhood (the place I live in) has those, but I don't take classes 3 No, my neighbourhood (the place I live in) doesn't have those 4 I don't know</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE).</p>			
<p>27</p>	<p>D3.5.4 Extra-curricular activities available / after-class learning centres</p>	<p>Difference in the share of migrant-background children and native children who pick answer #1 in at least one of survey items below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 Are there after-school activities (such as sports, arts, music, etc.) in your school? 1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there is nothing I can access 4 No, there are no such services at all 5 I don't know</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 Are there after-school activities (such as sports, arts, music, etc.) in your community / neighbourhood? 1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there is nothing I can access 4 No, there are no such services at all 5 I don't know</p>	<p>original</p>		<p>Children, adapted 6-9</p>

		<p>This question will be adapted to <u>children aged 6-9</u> as follows:</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 1 Are there after-school activities (such as sports, arts, music, etc.) in your school? 1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there are no such services at all 4 I don't know</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM 2 Are there after-school activities (such as sports, arts, music, etc.) in your community / neighbourhood? 1 Yes, and I do use them 2 Yes, but I do not use them 3 No, there are no such services at all 4 I don't know</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE).</p>			
28	D3.6.2 Counselling services at school	<p>Share of schools with some staff dedicated to psycho-social support or personal counselling, based on survey item below</p> <p>SURVEY ITEM How many staff does your school currently have in the following capacities? Please note this refers to staff hired specifically to conduct these tasks, which usually requires some specific training. For each category: Nr full time: ___ Nr part time: ___ a. Language support teachers b. Learning support teachers (exclude the ones counted in a.) c. Psycho-social support / personal counselling d. Academic counselling / guidance (exclude the ones counted in c.)</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from principals (IMMERSE)</p>	original		
29	D6.1 Experience/perception of negative attitudes	<p>B. Difference in the share of migrant-background children and native children who answer positively to survey item below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey</i></p> <p>SURVEY ITEM Do you ever avoid certain places (such as shops, cafes, public transportation, some particular neighbourhood, some places in school) for fear of being treated badly? Y/N/Sometimes</p> <p>IF YES OR SOMETIMES Is the reason for this related to any of the issues below? (multiple option) 1 Your culture (traditions, customs...)</p>	Based on EU-MIDIS and original follow-up		Children 10+

		<p>2 Your race, ethnicity (i.e. skin colour...) 3 Your religion 4 Your gender (male/female/other) 5 Your sexual orientation (the gender(s) you are attracted to) 6 Your age 7 Your social class 8 Other</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE). This question <u>will not be applied to children aged 6-9</u>.</p>			
30	<p>D6.2 Experience of harassment and/or physical violence (incl. bullying) outside family</p>	<p>Difference in share of migrant-background children and native children responding 2-5 in the survey item below <i>Note: "Migrant-background children" refers to foreign-born children and children with foreign-born parents (including mixed heritage). "Native" children refers to children born in the country of survey whose parents are also born in the country of survey.</i></p> <p>Have you ever been bullied in [host country] by schoolmates at your school, your neighbourhood or online? 1 No, never 2 It has happened to me a few times 3 It has happened to me many times</p> <p>Source: survey data to be collected from children (IMMERSE)</p>			